

CORDEX Task Force report on proposed actions, steps and timelines in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7

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List of acronyms

AFT	CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track
AR7	IPCC 7th Assessment Report
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CDNOT	CMIP Data Node Operations Team
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, UK
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CPM	Convection-Permitting Modelling (e.g. as in TF-CPM)
CPRCM	Convection-permitting regional climate model
CV	Controlled Vocabulary
DR	Data Request
DRS	Data Reference Syntax
ESD	Empirical-statistical Downscaling
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
ESGF-NG	ESGF Next Generation
ESM	Earth System Model
FPS	CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study
GCM	Global Climate Model
LBC	Lateral Boundary Conditions
LULC	Land use and land cover
LULCC	LULC changes
ML	Machine Learning
NCAR	National Center for Atmospheric Research, USA
OMDP	CLIVAR Ocean Model Development Panel
ORCM	Ocean Regional Climate Model

POC	CORDEX Point of Contact
RCM	Regional climate model
REF	CMIP Rapid Evaluation Framework
REP	Representative Emission Pathway
SAT	CORDEX Science Advisory Team
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathway
TF	CORDEX Task Force
VIA	Vulnerability, impacts and adaptation

Document version history

Version	Comment
2025-12-05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First public version • Update dates and references • Fix ES-Doc errata system availability • Update “Data publication” section with the latest progress • Update REF framework progress • Add new TF developments: experiment design to GitHub, collection of CORDEX-CMIP6 non-ESGF servers, ... • Other minor edits
2025-08-04	Initial version shared with the SAT for comments

1. Introduction

The latest cycle of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP7) is about to start producing a set of climate forcings and simulations to support scientific research and assessments by the climate community, climate services, governments, and the Seventh Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC AR7). Concurrently, CORDEX is in the midst of generating the CORDEX-CMIP6 ensemble, with several regional communities still underrepresented in this dataset. Recent efforts in developing protocols and technical documentation for CORDEX-CMIP6 have laid a foundation for the upcoming CORDEX-CMIP7. However, integrating the advancements in modelling strategies from both CMIP and CORDEX will be essential.

One of the primary goals of the Task Force (TF) in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7 was to evaluate whether CORDEX can and should adopt CMIP7 forcing in time to contribute to the next IPCC AR7 (publications should be accepted by the end of 2027). It is thus critical to balance the innovation and demand for CMIP7–forced data with the complexities of releasing two products (CORDEX-CMIP6 and CORDEX-CMIP7) simultaneously. This dual effort could potentially detract from the completeness of the CORDEX-CMIP6 ensemble. To align with the AR7 timeline, the CORDEX-CMIP7 protocols and technical documentation should be finalized by the time the first CMIP7 models become available for downscaling, expected in about one year (mid-2026).

Regardless of the timeline, CORDEX-CMIP7 will inevitably take shape in the coming years, requiring the community to be adequately prepared. In this document, we explore the necessary actions and steps to ensure a smooth transition to a CMIP7–driven CORDEX ensemble. Achieving this will require collaboration among diverse experts and consultation with the broader CORDEX community. The number and type of models used by the CORDEX community have increased and, for the next CMIP cycle, the experimental design must account for Regional Climate Models (RCMs) with coupled and uncoupled components, a resolution increase to convection-permitting (few-km) scale, and the extensive use of Empirical Statistical Downscaling (ESD) and Emulators benefiting from new Machine Learning techniques. Therefore, close coordination with other ongoing CORDEX TFs will be necessary to develop the new experimental design. For the most technical parts, we advocate for the creation of a Working Group tasked with developing the required actions/steps and maintaining the documentation and infrastructure.

With this working group in mind, we review the past efforts in preparing CORDEX-CMIP5 and the current CORDEX-CMIP6, providing links to a wealth of existing resources and discussing the new opportunities and challenges for CORDEX-CMIP7. We provide recommendations to move forward in a practical and scientifically sound way, taking into account the tight deadlines imposed by the IPCC cycle.

Apart from the review and discussion of the required steps in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7, some specific actions have been already carried out by the TF:

- Publication of existing CORDEX documentation with persistent identifiers and versioning in Zenodo¹.
- Migration and rewording of the initial CORDEX (-CMIP5) documentation from the IS-ENES project to the WCRP-CORDEX organization in Github².
- Update of the [CORDEX-CMIP6 Archiving Specifications for Dynamical Downscaling](#) and the [CORDEX experiment design for dynamical downscaling of CMIP6](#).
- Migration of the development of these documents to [GitHub](#), for a public track of changes and discussion with the community.
- Collection of regional-scale climate processes and metrics for climate model evaluation, in support of the GCM selection step (see Section 5.3).
- Collection of CORDEX publications in a [Zotero.org](#) library, where it can be accessed for different purposes and maintained collaboratively.
- [Collection of servers](#) which already provide public access to CORDEX-CMIP6 data.
- Preparation of a [form](#) to collect projects supporting the CORDEX activities (see Section 5.12)
- Community survey ([Appendix 1](#)) on potential commitments to support CORDEX-CMIP7 in time for AR7.
- Community survey ([Appendix 2](#)) on the climate forcing data sets used in CORDEX-CMIP6
- Preparation of a suitable call for members ([Appendix 3](#)) of the working group to handle the preparation of CORDEX-CMIP7 and beyond.

The document is structured by introducing the novelties in CMIP7 (Section 2) and CORDEX (Section 3), along with an overall view of the lessons learned in the preparation of CORDEX-CMIP6 (Section 4). The steps in preparation of CORDEX-CMIP7 are introduced next (Section 5), with a common structure describing the planning steps, implementation in previous CMIP cycles, a discussion of the opportunities and challenges in CMIP7, and recommendations to be considered by the CORDEX Science Advisory Team (SAT). We finalise analysing the synergies with other CORDEX TFs (Section 6) and the recommended timeline of the different steps in relation to the CMIP and IPCC timelines known to date (Section 7).

¹<https://zenodo.org/communities/wcrp-cordex>

²<https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/cordex-cmip5>

2. What is new in CMIP7?

Recently, different CMIP working groups have published several articles with updated information for CMIP7. The overview paper by [Dunne et al. \(2025\)](#) presents the scientific rationale in line with WCRP 2019–2028 Science Objectives, the experimental framework for CMIP7, an updated version of the mandatory Diagnostic, Evaluation and Characterization of Klima (DECK), and the newly introduced Assessment Fast track (AFT) that will be a subset of CMIP7 experiments to support upcoming assessments, such as IPCC AR7 and CORDEX, among other users. As stated in [Dunne et al. \(2025\)](#), the CMIP vision has been always the coordination of community-based efforts to answer key and timely climate science questions and the facilitation for delivery of relevant multi-model simulations through shared infrastructure for the benefit of the physical understanding, vulnerability, impacts and adaptations (VIA) analysis, national and international climate assessments, and society at large.

Some novel points for CMIP7 discussed in the article “An evolving Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase 7 (CMIP7) and Fast Track in support of future climate assessment” ([Dunne et al., 2025](#)) are listed in the CMIP web page <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phases/cmip7> and summarized here:

- CMIP7 includes a revised DECK based on the same experiments used in previous CMIP, but it has been expanded by adding a) the historical simulation, b) a small set of “fixed-SST” experiments to characterize effective radiative forcing, and c) an expanded protocol to facilitate participation with Earth System Models (ESMs) that close the carbon budget and are capable of running with interactive CO₂ forced by emissions (including positive, zero, and negative scenarios) in addition to prescribed concentrations. This will allow for more complete description and characterization.
- CMIP7 also introduces the new AFT Experiments to support both the direct needs of the climate research community for synthesis and physical science assessment as well as downstream climate services applications. The subset of simulations will include *near-term prediction and long-term projection* experiments that will provide critical information to satisfy the needs for both short and long term planning and for the impacts, mitigation and adaptation communities; it will also contain high temporal resolution forcing for regionally tailored information through dynamical and statistical downscaling such as CORDEX.
- CMIP7 will have updated, expanded, and improved historical forcings (solar radiation, volcanic eruption representation, aerosols, etc.) extended to at least 2021 and new scenario experiments.

Another CMIP7 paper that is under review is the Scenario Model Intercomparison Project for CMIP7 (ScenarioMIP-CMIP7) by [van Vuuren et al. \(2025\)](#) that describes the scenario experimental framework. An important innovation is that most scenarios are intended to be run, if possible, in emission-driven mode, providing a better representation of the earth system uncertainty space. The scenarios cover the period 2025–2100 (AD) with long-term extensions up to 2500 (AD). One of the goals of ScenarioMIP is to produce scenarios that can be useful to the IPCC AR7. This means that studies forming the basis of the assessment and relying on the new scenarios outcomes need to start appearing in the peer-reviewed literature in the 2026–2027 time frame.

The primary purpose of the ScenarioMIP is to provide emissions and land use pathways to drive ESMs. The scenarios should encompass a wide range of policy-relevant emission trajectories considered to be plausible/feasible. Up to now, **ScenarioMIP experiments** were driven by concentrations. As this does not account for uncertainty in the carbon cycle response to climate, the decision was made for CMIP7 to run most simulations preferably in emission driven mode (Sanderson et al., 2024). There will be six emission-driven scenarios of high priority (esm-scen7, with three high/medium and three low and very low scenarios) and three concentration-driven scenarios (scen7, with high to low concentrations), as described in Table 1 of [van Vuuren et al. \(2025\)](#). The three highest emission-driven scenarios are:

- High/Medium emission (esm-scen7-h) scenario is expected to result in forcings below SSP5–8.5.
- Medium emission (esm-scen7-m) scenario explores consequences of continuing current policies without modification.
- Medium-Low (esm-scen7-ml) scenario explores a delayed increase in mitigation efforts, short of the Paris temperature goals but achieving net-zero CO₂ emissions by the end of the century.

Van Vuuren et al. (2025) acknowledges the role of complex climate models and the possibility of reducing the computing burden by using emulators. However, at this point in time, it is envisioned that all ScenarioMIP scenarios will be run using ESMs. However, they do not exclude the possibility that, for specific projects, some climate variables and specific scenarios emulators can be used,

The High-Resolution Model Intercomparison Project phase 1 (HighResMIP1; Haarsma et al., 2016) was a new project within the CMIP6. HighResMIP1 provided a protocol for model simulations (both atmosphere-only and coupled from 12 modeling centers) to be consistently performed and compared to each other and with available observations. Given the broad impacts of the HighResMIP1 outcomes, and extensive needs for improved

high-resolution climate data in climate change impact assessments, CMIP7 will have the HighResMIP2 to continue providing important insights in time for the next IPCC report. The article under review “High-Resolution Model Intercomparison Project phase 2 (HighResMIP2) towards CMIP7” by [Roberts et al. \(2025\)](#) describes the improvements and extension of the previous works to address new science questions, and to further advance our understanding of the role of horizontal resolution (and hence process representation) in state-of-the-art climate simulations. Here we summarize some relevant points from this article:

- There are already 10 modeling groups that have proposed to contribute to HighResMIP2 with couple model simulations using forcings from CMIP6 or CMIP7; the planned atmospheric resolution varies from 25 to 9 km and the midlatitude ocean resolution varies from 25 to 5 km, as shown in Table 1 of Roberts et al. (2025). These increments may produce more accurate representation of the ocean's mesoscale, including eddies and boundary currents (e.g., Chang et al., 2020); enhancements in atmosphere resolution may produce more realistic climate extremes and upscale feedbacks (Scaife et al., 2019).
- The choice of model physics and dynamics settings with resolution (such as the treatment of atmospheric deep convection or implementation of aerosol forcing) is left to the modelling groups.

In contrast to the HiResMIP model simulations, the vast majority of models in CMIP6 had grid spacings of 100–200 km in the atmosphere and 50–100 km in the ocean. Our current understanding is that such resolutions (described as standard resolution) will likely remain typical in CMIP7 (Dunne et al., 2025), given historic rates of increase in model resolution (Hewitt et al., 2022). According to IPCC AR6 (2021; their [Figure 1.19](#)), CMIP increased from 37 standard models in CMIP5 to 50 in CMIP6. The information on the number of modeling centers participating in CMIP7 is anticipated to be finalized by late 2025.

In CMIP, the Climate Model Output Rewriter (CMOR) is the main software library used to translate raw model output into a standards-conformant form. It ensures CF conventions and CMIP controlled vocabularies, maps variables to the official tables, applies required naming and units, encodes dimensions and coordinates (including calendars and bounds), writes required global attributes and citations, and produces filenames and directory layouts consistent with the CMIP DRS (Data Reference Syntax). CMOR also enables validation (e.g., via PrePARE) to catch schema errors before publication, so that downstream services encounter predictable, machine-readable datasets. The ESGF publication workflow depends on these outcomes. The publishers expect datasets that already conform to the metadata tables and CVs (Controlled Vocabulary), carry the mandatory attributes, and follow the DRS/file naming rules. In short, CMORization is what

makes CMIP data “publishable” and discoverable in ESGF with uniform search facets and reliable subsetting.

For CMIP7, a new CMOR version 4 is currently under development and is expected to be the standard tool used for the publication of CMIP7 datasets. Version 4 will introduce changes towards CMIP7, including the removal of backward compatibility with the traditional CMIP6 CMOR tables (and hence, CORDEX-CMIP6 CMOR tables) formats which is why a new format for meta data is currently under development as well³. These CMOR tables bring together the CMIP7 CVs and data request in a machine readable format that is ready to be used by the CMOR library during the rewriting process.

In general, the detailed output specifications for CMIP7 are still pending. In fact, [those for CMIP6](#) were never fully finalized. This uncertainty also extends to the precise definition of what it means for data to be “*cmorized*” in practice, especially regarding the early publication of datasets during the CMIP7 Fast Track. In past phases, data that had been processed through the CMOR code was assumed to be “*cmorized*”. Likewise, data that successfully passed the PrePARE [quality assurance checks](#) (the CMOR checker) was treated as “*cmorized*”. Beyond these steps, no further validation was typically performed.

Another novelty in CMIP7 is the Data Request (DR) process, which introduces a streamlined, three-tiered structure to enhance clarity and usability: (1) the Core set comprises essential baseline climate variables expected from all models across experiments; (2) the Harmonised tier includes high-priority variables organized into five thematic areas—atmosphere, ocean & sea-ice, land & land-ice, Earth system (ES), and impacts & adaptation—developed collaboratively by expert teams to meet diverse scientific and policy needs; and (3) the Unharmonised tier offers flexibility for Model Intercomparison Projects (MIPs) and community activities to request additional variables beyond the harmonised scope. This new structure addresses previous concerns about complexity and documentation in CMIP6, aiming to balance comprehensive data provision with manageable workloads for modeling centers. The development process has been inclusive, incorporating extensive community consultation to ensure the data request aligns with the needs of various stakeholders, including those focused on regional downscaling, impact assessments, and climate services. The five thematic areas in point (2) will be also used in the Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF) to provide a systematic and rapid performance assessment of the expected models participating in the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track, supporting the seventh IPCC Assessment Report (AR7) cycle.

Relevant CMIP Task Teams to interact in the context of CORDEX-CMIP7:

³ <https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/cmip7-development-mip-tables>

- [Model documentation](#)
- [Climate forcings](#)
- [Model benchmarking](#)
- [CVs](#)

The latest news on what is new in CMIP7 regarding infrastructure was presented during a drop-in session on November 5, 2025 ([slides](#) and [recording](#) available).

3. How have CORDEX modelling approaches evolved since CORDEX-CMIP6?

Initially regional climate models (RCMs) used in CORDEX consisted only of atmospheric models coupled with simplified land-surface models, applied over a limited area and driven by global climate models. The objective was to provide climate information on much smaller scales than global climate models, enabling much greater detail and a more accurate representation of localised extreme events. This focus on the resolution may have come at the expense of incorporating greater model complexity into RCMs used in the first phase of CORDEX.

In CORDEX-CMIP5, the protocol specified that the initial CORDEX simulations would be carried out by regional atmospheric models, at a minimum horizontal resolution of 50 km, using prescribed SSTs, sea-ice fraction and land-use/vegetation maps. However, the protocol also allows for the possibility of coupling regional atmospheric models with ocean, sea-ice or dynamic vegetation models. For example, the Med-CORDEX initiative has enabled the development of coupled regional Earth system models (RESM), including the coupling with regional ocean models representing the Mediterranean Sea ([Ruti et al., 2016](#)).

However, it was recognised that some scientific challenges that CORDEX aims to address could be difficult to target with this general CORDEX framework. Therefore, more targeted experimental setups, called Flagship Pilot Studies (FPS) have been developed to address new scientific questions and enable new RCM capabilities. These have included, for example, FPSs on aerosols, land use changes, air-sea coupling, land-atmosphere-ocean interactions and urban representation (URB-RCC).

In CORDEX-CMIP6, the dynamical downscaling protocol still required as a minimum an atmospheric model coupled with a land-surface model, but the transition towards RESMs was encouraged. Even though the definition of what constitutes a RESM was not clear, these models typically include additional climate components such as ocean, interactive

aerosols, sea ice, dynamic vegetation, urban schemes, glaciers, or land hydrology. The aerosol forcing, which was a weakness in the CORDEX-CMIP5 protocol, was better addressed in CORDEX-CMIP6, with time-evolving aerosols being strongly recommended, but a static aerosol dataset considered as the minimum acceptable configuration. The potential benefits of these new components are multiple. On the one hand, the use of RESMs could improve the climate information produced over land, thanks to the improved representation of key forcings of regional climates (e.g., regional seas, aerosols, land use/land cover), the representation of new feedback loops, and the possibility to test new *what-if* scenarios. On the other hand, RESMs also enable us to produce new information for new components of the regional climate system, leading eventually to new knowledge, interactions with new modelling communities, the production of new regional climate datasets and regional climate information, as well as enhanced climate services to serve users. The addition of new components can, for example, be noted in the models used in EURO-CORDEX (Figure 1), with the addition of interactive aerosols, sea-ice treatments, lake models, urban parameterizations and dynamic vegetation in several RCMs (see also [Katragkou et al., 2024](#)). In CORDEX-CMIP6, the targeted resolutions were reduced to 25 and 12.5km, instead of 50km, allowing the regional CORDEX communities to choose the resolution that best fits their needs and resources, with a preference for higher resolutions when feasible.

Another important development during the CMIP cycles has also been the growing use of convection-permitting models at kilometer-scale resolutions, which explicitly permit atmospheric convection. This advancement represents a significant step towards improving the simulation of extreme events, such as intense precipitation, by better capturing processes that were previously parameterized in coarser model configurations.

Figure 1: Evolution of climate components represented in EURO-CORDEX regional climate models in CMIP5- and CMIP6-driven simulations.

For CORDEX-CMIP7, this trend towards higher resolution and increased complexity is expected to continue. A survey on new developments across the different CORDEX modeling groups was carried out in 2025 to learn about their intentions (Appendix 1). Out of the 24 responses received, 33 % of the groups have a new version of their model (compared to the one used in CORDEX-CMIP6) ready to be used. Notably, recent developments include the introduction of new climate components (urban representation, regional carbon cycle, ocean coupling), but also improvements in atmospheric physics (e.g. cloud microphysics). An increase in resolution is mentioned by only one group. The other two thirds of the groups would probably need more time to develop a new version of their model. The representation of climate forcings could for example be improved in the coming years in several RCMs, notably as far as aerosols and chemistry are concerned (see Appendix 2). The survey also enabled us to understand the main difficulties faced by the various groups. The limited storage capacity (42 %), lack of human resources (38 %), and associated funding (33 %) were among the most frequently cited responses, as were the lengthy CMORization process (29 %), and the development of models (25 %).

To summarise, the question of which models and which improvements in these models will be used for CORDEX-CMIP7 depends very much on the timetable imposed and the possibilities in terms of human resources, storage and funding. Today, 29 % of groups responding to the survey are confident they will be able to participate in the downscaling of CMIP7-AFT in time for AR7, with this figure rising to 58–75% if funding is obtained. In the longer term, beyond AR7, all the groups are considering participation in CORDEX-CMIP7, depending of course on funding, but with a minimum participation percentage of 46 % (compared with 29% for AR7-FT). It is important to note, that the simulations envisaged are highly variable from one domain to another, although there are plans to downscale most CORDEX domains (only MENA and CAS were not covered by the respondents).

Regarding ESD, a strong evolution of the methods has occurred thanks to the new efficient Machine Learning (ML) techniques, facilitating also new downscaling approaches such as RCM emulators. This new challenge is covered by the Task Force on Machine Learning (TF-ML; see also Section 6.4), so we invite the reader to follow the outcomes of TF-ML for a deeper review of recent progress.

4. Lessons learned from CORDEX-CMIP6

CORDEX has made a great effort in CORDEX-CMIP6 towards improving the interoperability with CMIP, by adopting many of the procedures in this initiative. Open, machine-readable formats have been adopted to collect the information for many of the steps described below. Version control and open discussions have been implemented via the CORDEX GitHub organization⁴, which is a new entry point for the CORDEX community to collaborate in an open environment. Some tasks have been automated to facilitate maintenance and, overall, this effort should pay off in CORDEX-CMIP7.

Zenodo⁵ has been adopted to track different versions of the technical documentation, simplifying the citation, and providing permanent digital object identifier (DOI) links. The documentation has been written in external editors, and saved as static PDF files. Detailed differences between versions are hard to track in this format. This point can be improved in CORDEX-CMIP7 by tracking the development of the documentation using frameworks based on plain text files. One example is the *mkdocs* framework recently adopted for CMIP7⁶. This system allows users to report issues in the documentation and discuss them openly, providing transparency in the protocol development.

⁴ <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/wcrp-cordex>

⁶ <https://wcrp-cmip.github.io/cmip7-guidance>

The FAIR principles⁷ should serve as the foundation for CORDEX-CMIP7 actions, ensuring openness, transparency, and machine-readable metadata formats. These principles should be applied to controlled vocabularies (CVs), tables, model documentation, archiving specifications, domain definitions, publications and more, while also being widely disseminated across relevant communities. FAIR principles should be integrated from the beginning in CORDEX-CMIP7, rather than making their fulfillment a task at some point.

5. Planning steps and specific actions

This section collects the specific steps and actions required in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7. Many of them (from section 5.7 on) are also pending for CORDEX-CMIP6, and a common framework could be adopted for both initiatives.

5.1 CMIP7 Data request (DR)

The CMIP data request is a list of GCM output variables, along with their frequencies, aggregation methods, and associated metadata that CMIP experiments should save. This step is crucial for CORDEX, as GCM output serves as the primary input for downscaling, and it is important to ensure that all required fields are requested. CORDEX, particularly in the case of dynamical downscaling, is quite demanding in terms of the number of fields, including three-dimensional model-level data at high frequency. This results in a large volume of data, which not all global modelling centers are willing to save, especially for multiple ensemble members. The CORDEX request is typically limited to a few ScenarioMIP experiments, along with the historical CMIP experiment.

In CMIP6, CORDEX was included as a diagnostic MIP (Gutowski et al., 2016) and its request was incorporated to the CMIP6 DR (Jukes et al., 2020) dedicated service at CEDA⁸. The total [CMIP6 data volume requested](#) by CORDEX was about 13 TB.

In CMIP7, the DR is managed by a dedicated CMIP Task Team (DRTT), which devised a Harmonized Thematic Variables process across 5 thematic areas (see [Section 2](#)). Each thematic area collected opportunities, that is, science enabled by the requested variables which is essential for a given MIP or user group. CORDEX lies under the Impacts & Adaptation thematic area (Ruane et al., 2025), where the opportunities were collected by means of a [Mural board](#), as an intermediate step for the thematic author team to fill the final Airtable database⁹ of Opportunities, Variable groups, Variables or Physical parameters. At

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁸ <https://clipc-services.ceda.ac.uk/dreq/u/CORDEX.html>

⁹ https://bit.ly/CMIP7-DReq-v1_2

the time of writing, the CMIP7 DR is in version 1.2.2, released on Jul 25th, 2025¹⁰. This version is considered final and will only be subject to updates for fixes to specific issues raised via the [Github repository](#).

CORDEX collected input [in a shared document](#) to help coordinate the input to the Mural board. The process resulted in two separate opportunities “Dynamical Downscaling” (split into 7 variable groups) and “Empirical Statistical Downscaling and Emulators” (4 variable groups), which can be explored in the corresponding Airtables ([DD](#), [ESD](#)). As compared to the CORDEX request for the CMIP6 DR, the CMIP7 DR includes many new variables for the atmospheric chemistry and the ocean and ocean biogeochemistry, which resulted from the contribution of the CORDEX Task Force on [Regional ocean climate projections](#).

The data request might still need careful checking. For example, v1.2.1 had some inconsistency in the lake area fraction (sftlaf) as compared to the definition in CORDEX, which was prior to the CMIP7 DR. We [opened an issue](#) and, in v1.2.2, they are already consistent. In Med-CORDEX, we found some inconsistencies in the cell_methods of ocean surface wave variables (new in CMIP7); this is still to be reported.

After v1.2.2, variable definitions in CMIP will be handed over from the DR task team to the CV task team, which will develop a more general WCRP Variable Registry GitHub. The proposal for longer term governance of the Variable Registry is still pending at the time of writing. Any changes post v1.2.2 should take place in the WCRP Variable Registry GitHub¹¹.

5.2 Experiment design

The CORDEX experiment design is the minimum set of instructions to coordinate the simulations carried out in the different regional domains. It is laid out in a document where mandatory and recommended practices are established regarding, for example, the simulation periods to be covered, the GHG scenarios to be used as forcing, the minimal spatial resolution, etc. Regional communities can adopt the experiment design as is, or adapt it for their purposes; but always towards being more restrictive. That is, mandatory instructions should not be relaxed. As a result of this Task Force, past documents with the experiment design have been published in Zenodo to better preserve them and to make them easily findable via unique DOIs for each different version.

In CORDEX-CMIP5, a very basic set of instructions was proposed as [experiment design](#) for dynamical downscaling. In fact, it was merged into a single document including also the archiving specifications (Section 5.6). A CORDEX-ESD [Experiment 1 protocol](#) was also envisaged, following the framework of the EU-COST action VALUE.

¹⁰ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip7-data-request-v1-2-2>

¹¹ <https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/Variable-Registry>

For CORDEX-CMIP6, the [experiment design for dynamical downscaling](#) was first released in 2021. Prior to that, two drafts were shared with the community for “blind” comments, to focus the improvements on common pitfalls. This experiment design included a separate [document](#) for the treatment of the aerosol forcing, prepared by the [FPS-Aerosol](#). The experiment design for [ESD](#) is still as a second draft, since Apr 2024.

Flagship Pilot Studies (FPS) have their own, more targeted, experimental setups. Some examples are the [FPS-CONV](#), [FPS-CPTP](#), etc. FPSs have explored new research avenues (Convection-permitting modelling, Machine learning ESD tools, Urban climate modelling, etc) that will likely feed back to the general experimental design to be set up for CORDEX-CMIP7. Some of these are also under heavy coordination efforts at the moment in several Task Forces. Therefore, the experiment design step will necessarily need to be carried out in view of the outcome of these other efforts. In the following, we just discuss some relevant aspects to take into account and, where appropriate, point to other strategic activities (TFs, FPSs) for deeper discussion. We also take into account the CORDEX White Papers on the scientific challenges for [dynamical downscaling](#) and [ESD](#).

For CORDEX-CMIP7, given the tight deadlines to contribute to AR7 and other assessments, it will be hardly possible for the modelling groups to perform strong model developments and for the community to agree on major changes to the experimental setup. On the other hand, new modelling approaches demand a careful experiment design to integrate all approaches in a consistent manner. Therefore, we advocate for a two tiered experiment design, as reported to the IPCC on February 20th (Briefing on CORDEX and AR7), in which there is:

- An “Assessment Fast Track” stream (CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT), essentially using the same CORDEX-CMIP6 models and minimally adapted protocols to provide some CMIP7-based information in time for AR7 and other assessments. If ready, ML-based techniques could contribute to expanding this stream. This initiative will feature a compact set of experiments targeting climate science priorities relevant to AR7 (e.g. overshoot scenarios), with results anticipated tentatively by mid-2027.
- A “Standard” stream (CORDEX-CMIP7) over a longer time frame, where new model and climate forcing developments are included, representing a next generation downscaling.

A first challenge in this setup is the compatibility of the two streams. As proposed above, CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT would be closer to CORDEX-CMIP6 in terms of protocols and specifications. This would also facilitate joint CORDEX-CMIP6/CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT analyses relevant for AR7. On the other hand, we need to ensure that CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT is compatible or part of CORDEX-CMIP7. But the latter will very likely need new specifications to fully adapt to the CMIP7 standards. Many CMIP7 technical details are still

unknown, so this issue will need further discussion in the future. In the following, several aspects of the experiment design are discussed, without attaching them specifically to a given stream.

One of the main aspects covered by the experimental setup is the definition of standard domains and recommended and minimal resolutions (grid spacing). The minimal resolution has increased from 50 km in CORDEX-CMIP5 to 25 km in CORDEX-CMIP6. A natural recommendation for a minimal resolution in CORDEX-CMIP7 would be to set it to 12 km. The recommended resolution can also be about this 12–10 km grid spacing as grids of ~6 km resolution would lay in the so-called “gray zone”, and it would be better skipped in favour of CP simulations in the range of 2–4 km, but these would need intermediate domains, and fall in the realm of the TF-CPM. A minimal resolution of 12 km can still be challenging for large domains and/or modelling groups with less resources. To maximise participation, especially for CORDEX-CMIP7–AFT, the same setup as in CORDEX-CMIP6 could be kept (25 km minimum, 12.5 km recommended).

Standard, continental domains have proved useful and regional communities are already organized around them. There are mechanisms already established to propose changes to those domains. Additionally, as CP simulations become standard in CORDEX, a new mechanism needs to be devised to propose and approve sub-continental domains. National domains play a key role at this scale as many CORDEX groups run on national funds with targeted interests. Attracting these downscaling efforts will increase the number of climate projections and modelling centres in CORDEX. Care should be taken in order not to exclude countries with less capacities, notably over large domains. The Africa domain has been the focus in both CORDEX-CMIP5 and CORDEX-CMIP6. In CORDEX-CMIP5, this was a success story, with many simulations contributed for this domain. In CORDEX-CMIP6, this focus region highlighted in the experiment design has been largely ignored by the community, and no simulation is currently available over Africa. The strategy to cover domains with few local resources and high vulnerability needs to be revisited. A tight integration of CORDEX-CORE into the general experiment design from the beginning could help in this regard.

CP simulations at continental scale have been carried out in different centres: SAM-4 ([NCAR-SAAG](#)), AFR-4 ([UKMO](#)), CONUS-404 ([NCAR](#)), NAM-4 ([ANL](#)), SEA-8 ([SINGV](#)), etc. Unfortunately, such efforts did not meet the CORDEX protocol for different reasons (e.g. due to using a Pseudo Global Warming -PGW- approach). Future experimental setups could be relaxed or extended to accommodate some of these downscaling efforts, so CORDEX extends the coordination to a wider community. Such particular discussion belongs to the TF-CPM, but other potential extensions could be considered regarding the bias adjustment of lateral boundary conditions (LBC) prior to downscaling ([Wamahu et al., 2025](#)), or the downscaling of time slices (e.g. GWLs). These pose their own new challenges

as different methodologies exist to bias adjust LBCs, and GWLs may limit downstream applications.

Dynamical downscaling is still central to CORDEX, with most survey participants ([Appendix 1](#)) focusing on this approach. Still, statistical approaches have also a central and complementary role, which has never been fully integrated in the CORDEX framework despite several attempts. The diversity of methodologies (Perfect prognosis, Model output statistics, Bias adjustment, hybrid methods, RCM emulators) and output nature might have played a role. Challenges include ([Gutierrez et al., 2022](#)) multivariate aspects, the progress in intercomparison frameworks and, generally, the distillation of robust climate information not only from these methods, but from all lines of evidence. Some of these challenges are being tackled in the ongoing CORDEX TF for Machine Learning (TF-ML), but we are also planning a POC meeting (end of 2025) focused on the better integration of ESD methods in the CORDEX framework. The outcomes of these initiatives will hopefully bring a clearer joint framework for CORDEX-CMIP7. In particular, RCM emulators are promising tools to explore natural variability. This might give a chance to downscaled climate (decadal) prediction, which was already considered in the early days of CORDEX¹², but disregarded due to the computational burden. Emulators, and ML in general, is also leading to a growing CORDEX community that will need to be integrated in the activities.

Dynamical downscaling has also progressed to a point (see [Section 3](#)) where the recommendations to increase the effort towards including additional model components (ocean, sea ice, glaciers, urban areas, lakes, vegetation/agriculture, land hydrology, aerosols and chemistry) might be turned to mandatory, at least for certain domains, model resolutions or scenarios (e.g. modelling glacier recovery could be key in overshoot scenarios). In this respect, the work of different past and ongoing FPSs (Air-sea, Aerosol, LUCAS, URB-RCC, CPTP, etc.) will be key to inform the experiment design, as well as the activity of the ongoing TF-Ocean and TF-CPM (see also [Section 6](#)). Specific dynamical downscaling approaches such as spectral nudging¹³ and variable-resolution global models only forced by the SST¹⁴ might need to be more carefully considered to be integrated with the rest of downscaling approaches.

Addressing the long-standing challenge of ensuring that forcing datasets are fully consistent with the driving CMIP GCMs should be a priority for CORDEX-CMIP7, if not for CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT. CMIP consistently uses input4MIPs¹⁵ datasets, but this is not the

¹² see e.g. section 6.5 in the Toulouse report (2009):

https://cordex.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/cordex2009_toulouse_report.pdf

¹³ <https://github.com/orgs/WCRP-CORDEX/discussions/13>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/simulation-status/issues/78>

¹⁵ <https://input4mips-cvs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/dataset-overviews>

case in CORDEX (Appendix 2). Some forcings are easier to adopt (e.g. solar irradiance) than others (e.g. land use changes, emissions), which would need a strong development effort. Regarding the land use data sets, some recommendations from FPS-LUCAS (D. Rechid) are:

- Consider land use & land cover (LULC) changes in ERA-driven simulations. It would be important that all models use the same LULCC dataset. Ideally, there would be a regional expert group which could transfer the LUCAS method to their respective CORDEX region, so that datasets are also consistent between regions, but could consider specific regional LULCC characteristics.
- Use the same LULCC datasets for the historical GCM-driven simulations.
- For the GCM-driven future climate change simulations, so far only human-driven land use changes have been considered in RCMs, but not climate-driven land cover changes (at least within LUCAS). It first would require new methods to derive maps which consider both human- and climate-driven LULCC. However, this would also add additional uncertainties. Thus, the recommendation would be to at least consider human-driven land use changes, consistent with land use change scenarios e.g. from SSPs or REPs.

Most CORDEX models are not able to deal with emissions and are not considering it in their near future development plans (Appendix 2). Also, GHG emission-driven GCMs will likely show strong variability in their future GHG evolution. This is a new source of uncertainty in CMIP7. In CORDEX-CMIP7, even if emissions-ready RCMs would be available, they will likely develop their own GHG concentration response, inconsistent with the driving GCM. In this situation, we would recommend, at least for CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT, to stick to concentration-driven GCMs to drive the RCMs, so using a consistent GHG forcing.

The selection of priority CMIP7 REP scenarios to simulate will be a major decision which needs to be taken relatively quickly for CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT. Some aspects to consider are:

- CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT and CORDEX-CMIP6 will coexist in time and both should be analysed together. Therefore, the REP scenarios prioritized should either complement the CORDEX-CMIP6 SSP1-2.6 and SSP3-7.0 with an alternative future not considered in SSPs (e.g. an overshoot scenario) or align with the existing scenarios (e.g. the High REP scenario, if this leads to a forcing close to SSP3-7.0).
- Scientifically, scenarios with a strong forcing (High, High overshoot) are preferred, since they lead to a clearer signal and also reach a variety of climatic conditions which is key e.g. to train emulators, which can then be used to explore other scenarios.

- The decision needs to consider different users' views and different needs (impacts, adaptation, mitigation communities), which lie beyond the CORDEX community and which typically demand realistic but also worst-case scenarios.

From the survey (Appendix 1), the CORDEX modelling community has no strong commitments towards particular scenarios. A potential way forward is to have a workshop or a POC meeting dedicated to REP scenario selection. POCs would collect needs from their respective communities and key talks could show the details of the new scenarios and their implications.

A final comment on the experiment design regarding the extent of the simulations. As we progress in the century, the year 2100 is closer, and a minimal extension to at least 2125 (100 years) should be considered, especially to better sample the evolution of overshoot scenarios. Even longer extensions could make sense in polar regions (e.g. up to 2300), but LBCs might not be available. Also, extensions back to GWLO (1850–1900) could be considered to better characterize the regional warming since preindustrial levels.

5.3 Driving GCM selection

The CORDEX community applies model selection for two main reasons. Firstly, GCM errors are well known to propagate through the downscaling methods and affect the suitability of regionalized, high-resolution model output data, thereby compromising all downstream applications. Secondly, the community cannot afford to downscale all available global climate model simulations and a limited number of model runs must therefore be chosen.

In order to guide informed model selection, a number of model selection criteria must be defined and the models be evaluated correspondingly. In CORDEX-CMIP5, this important working step was not coordinated in a systematic way and a GCM “ensemble of opportunity” was used in most CORDEX regions. CORDEX-CMIP6 has seen a number of coordinated GCM selection efforts for Europe ([Sobolowski et al. 2025](#)), North America ([Ashfaq et al. 2022](#), [Goldenson et al. 2023](#), [Matte et al. 2025](#)), South and Southeast Asia ([Nguyen et al. 2025](#)), South America ([Arias et al. 2025](#)), and Australia ([Di Virgilio et al. 2022](#), [Grosse et al. 2023](#)). For the example of EURO-CORDEX, the following set of selection criteria was established:

1. Data availability
2. Model Plausibility / Performance / Fidelity
3. Model Diversity / Independence
4. Spread of future outcomes / Climate Sensitivity

These criteria have been agreed on in this form or in a similar form in the other CORDEX regions. In support of the AR7 Assessment Fast Track, the CMIP [Model Benchmarking Task Team](#) (MB-TT) was created to provision a core set of diagnostics and metrics to compare GCMs against observations, currently on global or continental scale, on the basis of monthly data. The software developed to this end is the [Rapid Evaluation Framework](#) (REF, [Hoffman et al. 2025](#)), based on different existing frameworks (ESMvalTool, PMP, ILAMB, IOMB) that can be executed in a container, and will be run directly on the ESGF nodes in order to quickly evaluate newly available GCMs, beginning with those contributing the [CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track](#). The v1 release of the REF ([Hassler et al. 2025](#)) launched on October 7, 2025 consists of approximately 30 [diagnostics](#) (this is the corresponding [work-in-progress table](#)) that were discussed in a dedicated [Hackathon event](#) in March 2025. The MB-TT is currently considering new processes (aka diagnostics) and metrics to be included in the REF. In this context, we had a [series of meetings with the CORDEX POCs](#) (starting on February 27, 2025) to ask for regional-scale evaluation processes and corresponding metrics relevant in their domains. These led to a collection initially published on Zenodo on May 14, 2025 that can be applied to select GCMs whenever needed ([Brands et al. 2025](#)). Thereafter, a substantial part of the metrics published in this collection was included into a comprehensive Python toolkit developed by Moetasim Ashfaq for the TF CORDEX-CORE-CMIP6, and the associated performance, independence, and spread in future outcome results have already been calculated. These ongoing GCM selection efforts were reported to the MB-TT and the broader GCM evaluation community at the [Model selection – supporting downstream activities use of CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track](#) workshop on October 7, 2025. They are expected to be considered in the extension phase of the REF that is currently under way.

Meanwhile, several regional-scale diagnostics and metrics available from the [REF dashboard](#) can be used for providing “objective” GCM selection criteria whenever needed. However, the description and proper identification of some of the metrics used there is still unclear, a shortcoming expected to be resolved in the future.

There is also a [REF data request](#). The variables relevant for CORDEX not included there should be covered by the CORDEX opportunity sent to the CMIP7 data request (see Section 5.5). Based on this information, we can filter those GCMs that actually provide the data necessary for downscaling.

The aim for CORDEX-CMIP7 is to explore and condense the aforementioned regional GCM selection efforts into a single community approach using a common, accepted methodology, taking into account the perspective of other CMIP and Rifs task teams and Model Intercomparison Projects. To come to a consensus in this regard, we are currently organizing a multi-community side session about GCM selection to be held at the CMIP Community Workshop 2026 in Kyoto. If there is a substantial amount of CMIP7-AFT

scenario simulations available by then, we should be able to select driving GCMs for CORDEX shortly after this Workshop. A dedicated, CORDEX-only workshop on driving GCM selection will likely be needed to make a final decision.

5.4 Monitoring simulations

CORDEX simulation ensembles typically take a long time to complete (Figure 2) and they develop very differently in the different domains (Figure 3). Monitoring the simulation status and plans by the different modelling groups provides essential information to plan and balance the CORDEX grand-ensemble as it grows.

In CORDEX-CMIP5, there was no central monitoring system and each regional community managed internally the status of their simulations, typically exchanged during annual meetings.

For CORDEX-CMIP6, the CORDEX SAT made an effort to collect centrally the simulation plans; initially by means of a [Google Doc table](#), but then moved to machine-readable files under GitHub¹⁶, so anyone can produce their own status plots (e.g. Figures 2 and 3) out of this central information. Some regional communities that kept their own simulation status (e.g. MED) are moving to this central resource. The information collected allows to display [GCM-RCM-SSP combination matrices](#) for the different domains, or even to keep track of specific [experiments](#) designed by the regional communities. Datable [quick filters](#) are available in the simulation list to easily locate simulations by any of the fields requested, or to share unique URL searches; e.g. https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status/CMIP6_downscaling_plans.html?search=completed%20evaluation shows completed evaluation simulations.

¹⁶ <https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status>

Figure 2: Cumulative number of CORDEX simulations completed on different dates. The stacked bars show the number of simulations completed, running and planned as of 2025-07-04. The cumulative simulations for the future use information on expected completion dates from <https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status>.

Figure 3: Number of scenario simulations completed, running and planned by each of the regional CORDEX domains as of 2025-07-04, according to the information in <https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status>.

Of course, the information provided is only as good as the community keeps it updated with their simulation plans and status. The report of simulation plans is an entry card for model and institution registration, i.e. no model can be registered unless the simulations planned with it are known to the community. Unlike the CV registry, the simulation status collection is quite flexible and plans can be registered with tentative model identifiers or details to be decided (e.g. driving GCM or scenario). The idea is to facilitate the early emergence of as many CORDEX simulation plans as possible. Any detail can be updated at any time.

The same repository is already holding [plans and simulations for CORDEX-CMIP7](#) from an early stage. In fact, it already holds retrospective information files for CORDEX-CMIP5, using ESGF-derived information. A pending task is merging the information provided by the modelling groups with that of the ESGF as CORDEX-CMIP6 simulations start to be available there.

5.5 Data request

The CORDEX data request (DR) is the set of variables requested from the modelling groups to be saved in a format consistent with the [CORDEX archiving specifications](#) (see next section). The data request consists of a list of climate variables, along with their output frequency and other attributes, such as the corresponding variable name, long name,

standard name (i.e. the physical parameter according to the CF conventions), the aggregation in time and space, or the dimensionality of the variables. The development of the data request involves both the scientific task of selecting the variables to be included and their priorities, and the technical question of how to actually store or present the data request to the users.

For CORDEX-CMIP5, the DR was distributed as a PDF table¹⁷ maintained in a MS Excel file under the github organization of the EU-funded IS-ENES project¹⁸. As part of this Task Force, all CORDEX-CMIP5 documents have been collected under the WCRP-CORDEX organization in Github¹⁹ and updated to the current naming of this initial stage of CORDEX (CORDEX-CMIP5). This initial CORDEX DR was influenced by previous coordinated downscaling initiatives, such as the US NARCCAP program²⁰ or the EU-funded ENSEMBLES project²¹, which already provided standardized lists of RCM variables based on early CMIP conventions. Apart from the general CORDEX DR for regional domains, other initiatives, such as FPSs, maintained their own variable lists based on the general one (e.g. the [FPS-CONV variable list](#)).

For CORDEX-CMIP6, initially, an online [Google spreadsheet](#) was used (also served from the [cordex.org](#) website as a [MS Excel xlsx file](#)), but these documents are now obsolete and the data request is maintained as machine-readable CSV files in Github²² to track its development and allow automatic creation of consistent CMOR tables²³ and MS Excel files. A [tutorial document](#) provided a summary of the DR, but it is now also superseded by the [README file](#) shown as the front page in the DR repository. The selection of variables in the CORDEX-CMIP6 was based on the CORDEX data download statistics from ESGF²⁴ and through discussions with the CORDEX and impact modelling communities. In particular, the 17 CORE (mandatory) variables in the CORDEX-CMIP6 DR were selected as the most downloaded variables, plus the fixed fields for the terrain elevation (orog) and land-sea mask (sftlf). New variables and output frequencies arose from the dialogue with different modelling and user communities.

The CORDEX-CMIP6 DR still needs fine tuning. It is set up as a default data request that can be adopted “as is” by the different regional communities or activities (e.g. FPS). However, different CORDEX communities can also create their own DR²⁵, potentially with different

¹⁷ https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/cordex-cmip5/CORDEX_variables_requirement_table.pdf

¹⁸ <https://github.com/IS-ENES-Data/cordex>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/cordex-cmip5>

²⁰ <https://www.narccap.ucar.edu/data/data-tables.html>

²¹ https://ensemblesrt3.dmi.dk/RCM_output_table_final.xls

²² <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/data-request-table>

²³ <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/cordex-cmip6-cmor-tables>

²⁴ <https://esgf-ui.cmcc.it/esgf-dashboard-ui/cordex.html>

²⁵ Under <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/data-request-table/tree/main/data-request>

priorities, new/removed variables, etc. A [global DR file](#) keeps a list of all variables requested in any of the CORDEX initiatives, to make sure that the CMOR tables cover all variables requested. However, for the moment, most initiatives still keep their DR decentralized or have just adopted the default CORDEX-CMIP6 DR (Table 1). Some of them have been made machine-readable in the IMPETUS4CHANGE project ([FPS-URB-RCC](#), [FPS-CONV](#)), with some fixes applied. Moreover, a default DR is still missing for variables arising from components other than the atmosphere and land models. Currently, [work is ongoing](#) to integrate the ocean, aerosols, river, waves and ocean biogeochemistry data requests from Med-CORDEX.

Initiative	Data request
EURO-CORDEX	Default DR, but maintained as Google spreadsheet , and also in Zenodo
Med-CORDEX	Zenodo tables for atmosphere , ocean , river and aerosol variables
FPS-URB-RCC	Google spreadsheet
...	

Table 1: Links to the data requests from different CORDEX-CMIP6 initiatives.

For CORDEX-CMIP7, the DR will need to be reviewed and updated. We should ask what's missing and seek input from a wide variety of users to identify gaps to be filled to maximize the value of the data to the user community (e.g., the CORDEX-CMIP6 DR added hub-height winds for power generation). However, we should also consider past and present challenges and resource constraints faced by modeling groups (particularly storing large volumes of data), and see whether the DR needs to be reduced to avoid asking for too much and limiting the ability of modelers from around the globe to participate.

The CORDEX-CMIP6 DR is split into 3 components: Core (required), Tier 1 (strongly encouraged), and Tier 2 (optional). The Core set consists of the 15 most popular 2D surface variables, plus 2 important static fields (orography & land-sea mask). This list reflects the needs of climate impacts users, so we can expect that there will be no need to make dramatic changes. The distinction between Tier 1 and Tier 2 is that Tier 2 variables are requested for the benefit of specific CORDEX domains, or can be calculated by different methods that vary from model to model.

We should consider whether the current division of variables into Core, Tier 1, and Tier 2 continues to be the best way of organizing the DR, and whether the requirements are

being communicated clearly. One suggestion is split the sub-daily versions of the Core variables out into a new category, so that everything mandatory is in Core, and vice-versa.

The two biggest drivers of increased data volume are requests for 3D variables and sub-daily data. Sub-daily (hourly) data is strongly encouraged for Core variables and selected Tier 1 and Tier 2 variables, but not required, in recognition of the storage capacity limits faced by some groups. The DR should make recommendations about lossy compression. A document on lossy compression for CMIP7 is forthcoming, and should be reviewed.

3D variables are requested on a set of 10 standard pressure levels under Tier 1 and 8 more under Tier 2. One question to consider is whether it would be worth reducing the number of vertical levels to make space for vertical integral quantities (e.g., IVT), which are currently missing from the DR. Note that vertical integrals require computationally demanding post-processing and can be computed in a number of different ways, so they may belong under Tier 2.

The CORDEX-CMIP6 DR consists only of atmospheric variables. The CORDEX-CMIP7 DR should include variables from land and ocean components from the beginning, possibly others. The importance of non-atmospheric components may vary across different domains. Land cover types may also be an important factor, especially for urban variables.

5.6 Archiving specifications

The CORDEX Archive Design (AD) is a text document that specifies technical details of the structure, content, and format of the CORDEX archive and the files it contains. These rules and guidelines tell modeling centers how to organize, name, and describe their climate model data so that it can be shared and compared with other model data, especially through publication via the ESGF.

In CORDEX-CMIP5, the [archiving specifications](#) were defined to ensure that datasets produced by different regional climate modeling groups were consistent, standardized, and interoperable. They were mostly based on the specifications for [NARCCAP](#). These specifications covered key aspects such as file structure, naming conventions, metadata standards, data formats, and controlled vocabularies (CV), and were primarily based on the CF metadata conventions and the [CMIP5 Data Reference Syntax](#) (DRS).

The CORDEX-CMIP5 AD was provided as a versioned PDF with differences from previous versions highlighted. Like the DR, for CORDEX-CMIP6 it was added to the WCRP-CORDEX github repository, and has been [published via Zenodo](#). The sections of the AD are:

- 1) DRS elements: the controlled vocabulary elements used to systematically construct filenames and directory paths so that data ingestion into the ESGF and other software systems can be automated.
- 2) Global attributes: a table of metadata information that should be included in the netCDF files as global attributes.
- 3) File naming: the rules for constructing filenames from DRS elements
- 4) ESGF directory structure: the rules for organizing files into a directory tree using DRS elements.
- 5) File format: a specification of the file format (CF-compliant netCDF-4 classic data model), the data contained in each file, numerical precision of the data, and recommendations regarding basic data compression settings.
- 6) CORDEX domains and horizontal coordinates: specifications for handling spatial aspects of the data like relaxation zones and staggered grids. This also includes many details about how to describe the native / projected coordinate system used by the RCM, which can vary from model to model.
- 7) Time coordinate: specifications for how to label the time dimension of the data.
- 8) Time period for each data file: how much time to span in each file.
- 9) License: requirements for choosing a license for data used by others.
- 10) Registration: instructions on how to register the simulations for inclusion in the ESGF archive
- 11) ESGF Search Facets mapping: how to map ESGF search elements designed for CMIP6 to CORDEX. This is the first section of the document that doesn't provide rules for modelers to follow.
- 12) User support: instructions on how to create a github issue in the relevant repository.
- 13) Examples: CDL (plain text) representation of how the headers of correctly-formatted netCDF files should look. Many modeling groups use the examples as templates for determining how to format their data, so it is essential that these be correct.
- 14) Version history: a list of changes to the specifications.

During the transition to CORDEX-CMIP6, a lot of guidance was naturally inherited from the [CMIP6 Participation Guidance for Modelers](#), including the organization of controlled vocabulary and CMOR tables in dedicated GitHub repositories. The CORDEX-CMIP6 AD was based on the CORDEX-CMIP5 AD, and the same approach is likely to apply to the transition to CORDEX-CMIP7. However, during the early evaluation phase of CORDEX-CMIP6, it became evident that the initial AD was, in some aspects, unclear or did not fully meet the modelers' requirements. As a result, the AD had to be updated to ensure, for example, compatibility with ESGF. Current issues and proposed changes are now

being tracked in a dedicated GitHub repository²⁶. At present, it remains unclear how to handle these updates in cases where model data has already been prepared for publication according to outdated specifications. The transition to CORDEX-CMIP7 will again need to closely follow any changes occurring in the shift from CMIP6 to CMIP7²⁷, particularly regarding CF compliance and controlled vocabularies (CVs). This alignment is essential, as CORDEX has traditionally adhered to the standards of the driving MIPs to ensure compatibility. Another possibility is to ensure compatibility between CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT and CORDEX-CMIP6, to facilitate common analyses for AR7. Furthermore, any notable changes should be clearly highlighted to ensure that users familiar with the previous versions—who may be working largely from memory—can quickly identify the differences.

However, it will also be important to evaluate whether existing and newly developed tables and software components implementing AD are compatible and can be reused for CORDEX-CMIP7. Such reuse would significantly accelerate the transition to a CORDEX-CMIP7 AD.

Some items of note:

- 1) The rise of data storage and analysis in the cloud has increased the prominence of the Zarr file format. Conversion of data from netCDF to Zarr should be straightforward, but it would be worth checking whether the specification should be modified to better accommodate the likely call for CORDEX data to be made available in the cloud.
- 2) NetCDF4 supports data chunking, which controls storage patterns within a netCDF file. Chunking can have a dramatic impact on access speed when reading data from disk, which is very important for different applications (e.g. Machine Learning). The AD should make some recommendations about data chunking patterns. Unfortunately, no chunking pattern will handle all possible access patterns well, and compromise chunking schemes that attempt to support all access patterns adequately can prove to be poor at all of them. One possibility would be to follow the NCO software toolkit “rd1” chunking pattern, where chunksize equals dimension size for all dimensions except the record (time) dimension, where it has size 1, leading to efficient reading of individual timesteps across all space. See a recent discussion on this [here](#). Related to this, CMIP is considering re-packing the data prior to publication to improve read-performance, especially for remote access (see [cmip7repack](#)).

²⁶ <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/archive-specifications/issues>

²⁷ <https://wcrp-cmip.github.io/cmip7-guidance>

- 3) Some recommendations regarding [lossy compression](#) of the data could also lead to significant reductions in storage needs. A careful selection of the number of significant digits to retain per variable will be needed to take full advantage of this method, but any conservative truncation will reduce file sizes. If considered per variable, it could be part of the data request information.
- 4) The HEALPix projection is emerging as an important method for combining geophysical datasets on different grids. Similar to the Zarr file format, the TF should evaluate whether there are any upcoming [modifications to the CF Conventions](#) that would improve interoperability with HEALPix.
- 5) There are upcoming changes to the CF metadata standard that will clarify how different calendars handle leap seconds (or don't). Because model data is idealized, it will likely be the case that the specification will want to require that models using a “normal” calendar (i.e., with leap years, not a 365_day or 360_day calendar) should set the calendar attribute of the time coordinate to `proleptic_gregorian` (which does not have leap seconds) rather than to `standard` (for which it is unknown whether or not there are leap seconds). The TF should check the latest version of CF and update the spec accordingly.

5.7 Model documentation

Model documentation refers to the detailed description of the models participating in the different CORDEX activities. It should provide CORDEX users a clear view of the model components and their configuration. Ideally, it should be homogeneous across models, so they can be easily compared with each other. In particular, the differences between different configurations of the same modelling system should be easily spotted. Peer reviewed publications and technical reports describing the model are useful resources to learn about the full details of a model, and are generally used as references for further information in the model documentation.

In CORDEX-CMIP5, there was no centralized model documentation system. Each regional community followed its own approach (Table 2). For the RCMs participating in the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) contract PRINCIPLES (C3S_34b Lot2), there was an [ES-DOC](#) pilot experience to store the model documentation. ES-Doc is now down and unfixable²⁸. There are no plans to carry on maintenance due to lack of funds and a new system is being devised based on EMD (see below). Old model metadata is locked in compressed files (available in github <https://github.com/es-doc>) and only decipherable by a particular outdated library. The original information collected in excel files is available to be processed again. An important lesson learned from this experience is the need to rely on open, machine- and human-readable standards for model documentation. For

²⁸ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-model-and-experiment-documentation/#es-doc>

CORDEX-CMIP5 in general, a great effort was needed during the IPCC AR6 to collect model details from the modelling centers. This effort resulted in a table (Annex II: models, in the AR6 WGI report), which is also available in [Zenodo](#), where it can be updated as needed ([Diez-Sierra et al., 2022](#)). This is the most comprehensive model documentation available for CORDEX-CMIP5.

In CORDEX-CMIP6, there is still no centralized model documentation approach. Table 2 also lists some documentation resources used in the different regional communities for this MIP era. The model documentation step is still ongoing for CORDEX-CMIP6. Regardless of the technical solution to store the information, a key work yet to do is to decide *which* information will be stored. On model registration, a flexible approach was used, letting the modelling groups point with a URL (`further_info_url`) to their desired source of documentation. However, this leads to heterogeneous documentation, not really usable to compare models or to assess their fitness-for-purpose for a particular application. Also, the details of the exact model configurations used are commonly not publicly available, and generic URLs to the model website or the latest publication are provided.

One key aspect of model documentation is how to ensure that it is consistent with the info provided in the metadata of the files and elsewhere. It can be very confusing to find contradictory information in different places about the same `source_id`. This is something CMIP is also working on, and there might be a solution in place by the time of CORDEX-CMIP7. Also, we need to consider when to ask for model documentation to the modelling centers (e.g. before model registration, before data publication), taking into account that it could delay the step we use as a checkpoint, especially if many details are requested.

With the failure of ES-DOC, CMIP7 was also facing model documentation problems. In this respect, CMIP has recently developed a new Essential Model Documentation (EMD, currently [v0.992](#)) as part of their Climate Model Documentation Task Team (CMDTT). This effort is much less ambitious than ES-DOC in terms of the amount of information collected from each model. It is also general enough to be adopted by, or at least to be easily adapted to, CORDEX models. We highly recommend adopting EMD for CORDEX-CMIP7, extending it if necessary. Currently, there is no implementation of EMD, but will likely be fitted in the [WCRP Universe json files](#) (note the `esgvoc` branch, for the moment). In Med-CORDEX, a first attempt has been made to implement a model documentation based on a Jekyll website²⁹ maintained in Github³⁰ and adopting and extending the current EMD. It combines a YAML preamble to store metadata following the EMD with a flexible Markdown text formatting for the body of the model description. The goal was to keep

²⁹ <https://med-cordex.github.io/model-documentation>

³⁰ <https://github.com/Med-CORDEX/model-documentation>

both machine- and human-readability of the source files.

One of the potential points to extend the EMD for CORDEX is regarding the input forcing data sets. In CMIP, it is taken for granted that the modelling centers use the input4MIPs data sets but, according to the survey run as part of this TF (see [Appendix 2](#)), this is not the case in CORDEX. Therefore, it would be advisable to include information regarding the forcing inputs used, as these can be key to interpret the results.

Initiative	MIP era	Model documentation
CORDEX	CMIP5	Table in Zenodo maintained as Google Document
EURO-CORDEX	CMIP6	Table in Zenodo maintained as Google Spreadsheet
Med-CORDEX	CMIP5	System maintained by the HyMeX project with predefined form.
	CMIP6	Github-maintained website with free-text description plus machine-readable metadata preamble
CORDEX East Asia	CMIP5	Website: https://cordex-ea.climate.go.kr/cordex/models.do with free text model descriptions (common sections and extension)
	CMIP6	

Table 2: Links to CORDEX models documentation for different initiatives.

5.8 Quality Control

CORDEX Quality Control (QC) ensures that published datasets comply with CF conventions and [CORDEX archiving specifications](#) (see above). This compliance allows users to trust that the datasets are compatible with standard CF-compliant tools and analysis scripts. Adherence to CF conventions includes using only registered vocabularies for variables and coordinates—for example, the correct use of the standard_name attribute and valid area types.

Ensuring alignment with standard controlled vocabularies (CVs) and conventions makes CORDEX datasets usable across a broad range of standard metric tools. CORDEX QC also includes specific checks for consistency within domain specifications.

It is important to note that this quality control process does not assess scientific validity. Instead, it focuses on technical compliance, with minor exceptions such as verifying that values (e.g., temperature) fall within expected ranges.

In the CORDEX-CMIP5 phase, quality checks were primarily performed during the data publication process at the respective ESGF data nodes. Datasets that failed QC at these nodes were rejected and not published. The main tool used was [QA-DKRZ](#), developed by DKRZ, which could also validate CORDEX-specific requirements such as grid definitions. However, this tool has since been deprecated.

In addition to automated checks, CORDEX-CMIP5 included a manual QC process based on a [checklist](#) to ensure basic compliance. If a dataset needed to be retracted from the ESGF, this was typically documented through the Earth System Documentation ([es-doc](#)) service.

However, despite the existing efforts, the CORDEX-CMIP5 datasets proved to be [less compliant](#) with controlled vocabularies (CVs) and archiving specifications than initially expected. This lack of consistency posed challenges for the automated processing and analysis of large ensemble datasets. These issues only became fully apparent once the data were shared and exchanged through the ESGF and evaluated across different modeling centers. A key reason appears to be the use of varying QA strategies at different ESGF data nodes, leading to inconsistent levels of quality control and validation.

With the transition to CMIP6, QA-DKRZ was deprecated. As a result, several publicly available compliance checkers—primarily focused on CF compliance—were evaluated for use with CORDEX-CMIP6 datasets. These included:

- [PrePARE](#)
- [CEDA cf-checker](#)
- [IOOS compliance-checker](#)

Although PrePARE became the primary tool for CMIP6 dataset validation, it is [not suitable](#) or flexible enough to be effectively applied to CORDEX datasets without significant effort. A more general-purpose controlled vocabulary (CV) checker may be included in the upcoming [CMOR4 library](#), expected by the end of 2025.

At present, no dedicated QC tool exists that can handle arbitrary controlled vocabularies. However, there is ongoing [discussion](#) around leveraging the [IOOS compliance checker](#), which is anticipated to evolve in alignment with [CF-1.11](#) standards.

In parallel, a collaborative effort is underway to develop a plugin—[cc-plugin-cc6](#)—based on the compliance-checker framework. This plugin is designed to be flexible, supporting multiple MIP-specific CVs in addition to the CF compliance checks already provided by the compliance-checker.

Currently, the EURO-CORDEX community has implemented the [cc-plugin-cc6](#) as part of its QA process for the [joint evaluation](#) activities under CORDEX-CMIP6. In this effort, a large number of ensemble simulation datasets from various modeling groups are currently

collected at a dedicated data node at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC). This staging area allows for preliminary quality control and technical validation before the datasets are formally published to the ESGF via DKRZ.

This workflow ensures that data undergoes a consistent QC process and helps identify and resolve potential compliance issues early, facilitating smoother and more reliable publication. It also supports more coordinated evaluation and intercomparison activities across the CORDEX-CMIP6 community.

In the context of CMIP7, there is ongoing debate about whether quality assurance and quality control should be a prerequisite for publishing data to the ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation). This topic was prominently discussed during the WIP (WGCM Infrastructure Panel) meeting on February 25th, 2025.

A key question is where and by whom the QA/QC process should be carried out. Many data publishers and ESGF node managers argue that QA should be performed at the modeling centers—before data is transferred to ESGF nodes—to avoid wasting bandwidth and storage space on non-compliant datasets.

The urgency of some projects, such as the AR7 fast-track, complicates this issue, as they often proceed without waiting for full QA/QC validation. However, this raises concerns—what happens if a bug prevents a dataset from passing QA? In such cases, publication would be delayed until the issue is resolved and valid data is provided.

To support improved QA/QC workflows, DKRZ plans to contribute to quality control efforts for CORDEX-CMIP6/UDAG and the upcoming CMIP7/CAP7. As part of a broader initiative, French colleagues are currently developing a general-purpose [ESGF-QC](#) application under a C3S project. This tool is intended to serve multiple projects, including CORDEX-CMIP6 and, eventually, CORDEX-CMIP7. The new QC tool is based on a fork of the IOOS compliance-checker and aims to offer flexible, extensible validation mechanisms for a variety of controlled vocabularies and project-specific requirements. DKRZ is actively contributing to its development to ensure it meets the specific needs of the CORDEX and CMIP communities.

5.9 User guidelines

User guidelines are key as supporting material of the simulation data generated within CORDEX. Unlike technical model documentation or research papers, they provide basic information on model output data meaning and consider the whole ensemble, helping users understand the fitness of different approaches, models or sub-ensembles for particular purposes. Technical language is avoided to reach as wide an audience as

possible. User guidelines can be shaped as a document, but also as collections of Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ).

In CORDEX-CMIP5, several guidelines were prepared by different regional communities (Table 3). The CORDEX FAQ at cordex.org focuses mainly on technical data access and processing questions, rather than data meaning and usability.

Initiative	User guidelines
CORDEX	https://cordex.org/faq/faq-data-and-access
EURO-CORDEX	Guidance for EURO-CORDEX climate projections data use (v1.1, Feb-2021)
NA-CORDEX	https://na-cordex.org/guidance-data-use.html
...	

Table 3: Links to CORDEX models documentation for different initiatives.

No guidelines are currently available specifically for CORDEX-CMIP6. However, there is a current effort, e.g. in Europe, to update the existing guidelines to the particularities of CMIP6 and the ensemble design in EURO-CORDEX-CMIP6. The general CORDEX FAQ section also needs maintenance, as some of the questions are outdated and point to resources (e.g. Terms of Use) for CORDEX-CMIP5.

A new joint task team on “Responsible Data Use” has been setup by CMIP and RIFS³¹, seeking to reduce data misuse by developing recommendations for better means of documenting the limitations of model outputs for various key applications. They plan to gather existing information on downstream usage of model output and engage both modellers and users to develop optimal communication channels for appropriate use of climate model output data. This effort aligns well with the CORDEX needs in this matter and a follow up will be necessary to ensure that the CORDEX modelling methodologies are considered; both as a user of global model output and as a producer of regional model output. Swen Brands is the current CORDEX representative in this task team.

5.10 Data publication

CORDEX data publication refers to the process of making model output, following the archiving specifications (Section 5.6), available publicly. This has been typically done via the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF), a global network for sharing and accessing climate and Earth system data, supporting not only CORDEX, but also CMIP and other

³¹ <https://www.wcrp-rifs.org/activities/working-groups/responsible-data-use>

initiatives. CORDEX data publication entails technical work by the ESGF administrators to configure their nodes to support the CORDEX DRS. The configuration feeds from the CORDEX CVs and thus needs feedback between CORDEX and ESGF, and requires models (source_id's) to be registered prior to publication.

To date, only CORDEX-CMIP5 data have been published to ESGF. A global configuration file is available³², but local ESGF nodes might have modified versions to allow the publication of specific data sets. Apart from the Domain activity, data from other activities, such as [CORDEX-Adjust](#) or [CORDEX FPS-CONV](#), have been published on ESGF. Conversely, there are CORDEX-CMIP5 data published out of the ESGF. Notably, Med-CORDEX data were never published to ESGF and relied on their own server³³ and registration process to access the data. Data for other domains have also been replicated in other non-ESGF servers. For instance, NCAR keeps a copy of the data for the North American domain³⁴, but reformatted, not following the CORDEX DRS. Some monthly EURO-CORDEX data are available on the cloud, via the Amazon Web Services (AWS) open data³⁵, as are a subset of daily NA-CORDEX data in Zarr format³⁶. This simplifies the access to portions of the data. The Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS³⁷) also holds a copy of some commonly used daily variables from CORDEX-CMIP5 and has gone through an additional quality control ([Diez-Sierra et al., 2022](#)).

Data publication on ESGF for CORDEX-CMIP6 is still pending. Some data are available for specific domains via dedicated servers (e.g. in [AUS](#); even [regridded and bias adjusted](#) data), but ESGF configuration to support publication of CORDEX-CMIP6 data is [still in testing phase](#). As an interim solution, in the TF-CMIP7 we started [collecting servers](#) which already provide access to CORDEX-CMIP6 data. The ESGF itself is currently going through deep changes. ESGF 1.5 is the current stable version, but [ESGF Next Generation](#) (ESGF-NG) is [expected](#) to be available after December 2025, modernizing the system with a cloud-native architecture, improved scalability, and enhanced [user workflows](#). The [old system](#) will need to be down shortly after. Under the current resource constraints, CORDEX-CMIP5 data will not be immediately migrated to ESGF-NG; this needs to be handled to maintain access. By the end of Aug. 2025, there was a meeting between TF-CMIP7 and ESGvoc (L. Troussellier) to discuss the requirements to ingest the CORDEX-CMIP6 CV into ESGvoc and enable publication on ESGF-NG. This work is now [ongoing](#), along with the preparation of the rest of the [steps to have CORDEX data published on ESGF-NG](#) by early 2026.

³² <https://github.com/ESGF/config/blob/master/publisher-configs/ini/esg.cordex.ini>

³³ <https://www.medcordex.eu/medcordex.php>

³⁴ <https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/d316009/dataaccess>

³⁵ <https://registry.opendata.aws/euro-cordex>

³⁶ <https://registry.opendata.aws/ncar-na-cordex>

³⁷ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/projections-cordex-domains-single-levels>

Regardless of the technical difficulties of ESGF node configuration, a major challenge for CORDEX is to locate ESGF nodes willing to store the output, which, for CORDEX-CMIP6, is estimated to be about **8 PB** considering Core and Tier1 variables. The limited data storage capability of the CORDEX modelling groups is the most significant barrier found during CORDEX-CMIP6 (see [Appendix 1](#)). Some ESGF nodes are willing to store the output from specific domains or modelling groups, but this still leaves some CORDEX output with no destination node. In order to locate ESGF nodes willing to take CORDEX data, two different surveys have been carried out: one from this task force, distributed via the CORDEX POCs, and another one in collaboration with CMIP IPO, asking for the [willingness to store CMIP and CORDEX data](#) and distributed via de CDNOT ([Petrie et al., 2021](#)). The former collected contact point details and comments regarding the possibility to host CORDEX-CMIP6 data for each node. Contact information is not reproduced here³⁸, but the few nodes replying and their comments are shown in Table 4.

Dom.	ESGF Node	Contact point	Comments
AUS	esgf.nci.org.au	Ben Evans	Hosting data (as the primary ESGF node) for the institutes that we have storage contracts with: all AUS-20i except IRD-MF
EUR	data.meteo.unican.es	Antonio Cofiño	At least UCAN data. Might store some others.
EUR	esg-dn1.nsc.liu.se	Prashanth D. Rao	Only HCLIM43-ALADIN simulations generated by SMHI
EUR	esgf-ictp.hpc.cineca.it		Currently down due to Bologna flooding
EUR	esgf-node2.cmcc.it		Will store CMCC data. Need to check whether other data could be taken
EUR	esgf.dwd.de		No CORDEX data storage planned
EUR	esgf1.dkrz.de	Stephan Kindermann	In principle, only data from German modelling groups.
EUR	vesg.ipsl.upmc.fr	G. Levvasseur	(at least Med-CORDEX, EURO-CORDEX, Central America, Australasia) with French models (ALADIN, RCSM, AROME)
WAS	esg-cccr.tropmet.res.in	Sandip Ingle	The CCCR-IITM ESGF data node will be able to host the CORDEX-CMIP6 South Asia domain simulations

³⁸ They are kept by the TF team and will be handed over to the upcoming WG.

Table 4: Information on active CORDEX ESGF nodes and plans to store CORDEX-CMIP6 as collected via the CORDEX POCs.

The survey conducted by the CMIP IPO (Table 5) was responded to by a few more node administrators but the answers do not always match. Total storage allocated for CORDEX-CMIP6 among the respondents is 3.340 PB. One potential way forward is to contact again all respondents to both surveys, showing the summary of the expected storage, and requesting again the maximum storage that they can allocate for CORDEX-CMIP6 and CORDEX-CMIP7. Another pending activity is to estimate the storage covered by the comments in Table 4, as large fractions of the total storage could be already covered (e.g. the AUS simulations -1.3 PB- are covered by the NCI node, even if no exact space allocation was provided in the CMIP IPO survey).

Primary c...	What is the node identity?	Curren...	Plans for 2025 and beyond	Which active projects are associated with th...	Which archival projects...	CORDEX5 ...	CORDEX6...
Marco Puccini	https://esgf-ictp.hpc.cineca.it	Other	Continue to host existing data	CORDEX-CMIP6	Other		3,000
Sandip Ingle	https://esgf-cccr.tropmet.res.in	Hard Disk	Continue to host existing data CMIP7 publication (and replication)	CMIP6 CMIP7 Other	CORDEX-CMIP5	0,200	0,200
Marie-Pierre Moine	esgf1.umr-cnrm.fr	Hard Disk	Other	CMIP6 CORDEX-CMIP6	CMIP5 CORDEX-CMIP5	0,100	0,100
Katharina Berger	esgf1.dkrz.de/esgf3.dkrz.de/esgf-data.dkrz.de	Other	CMIP7 publication (and replication) Continue to host existing data	CORDEX-CMIP6 input4MIPs Other CMIP6	CMIP5	0,020	0,020
Charlotte Pascoe	https://esgf-vui.ceda.ac.uk	Tape Drive	Continue to host existing data CMIP7 publication (and replication)	CMIP6 CMIP6Plus CMIP7 input4MIPs obs4MIPs CORDEX-CMIP7 CORDEX-CMIP6	CMIP3 CMIP5 CORDEX-CMIP5	0,020	0,020
Antonio S. Cofino	https://data.meteo.unican.es	Hard Disk	Continue to host existing data Provision of compute alongside data for users	CORDEX-CMIP7 Other	CORDEX-CMIP5		
Guillaume Levasseur	https://esgf-node.iaps.uomc.fr	Hard Disk	CMIP7 publication (and replication) Provision of compute alongside data for users	CMIP6 CMIP6Plus CMIP7 CORDEX-CMIP6 CORDEX-CMIP7 Other	CMIP5 CORDEX-CMIP5	0,070	
Zach Price	https://esgf-node.ornl.gov	Tape Drive	CMIP7 publication (and replication) Continue to host existing data	Other CORDEX-CMIP7 CORDEX-CMIP6 obs4MIPs input4MIPs CMIP7 CMIP6Plus	CMIP3 CMIP4 CMIP5 CORDEX-CMIP5 Other		
Logan Macdonald	https://crd-esgf-drc.ec.gc.ca	Hard Disk	Continue to host existing data CMIP7 publication (and replication)	CMIP6 CORDEX-CMIP6	CMIP5		
Ole B. Christensen	https://cordexeso.dmi.dk/	Hard Disk	Continue to host existing data	Other	CORDEX-CMIP5	0,070	
DWD ESGF Team	https://esgf-data.dwd.de/	Tape Drive	CMIP7 publication (and replication) CORDEX-CMIP7	CMIP6 CMIP7 CORDEX-CMIP6 CORDEX-CMIP7	Other		
Andrew Robinson	https://esgf.nci.org.au/	Hard Disk	CMIP7 publication (and replication) CORDEX-CMIP7	CMIP6 CMIP6Plus CMIP7 input4MIPs obs4MIPs CORDEX-CMIP6 CORDEX-CMIP7	CMIP3 CMIP5 CORDEX-CMIP5	0,100	
Alina Barbu	https://esgf1.umr-cnrm.fr	Other	Continue to host existing data Other	CMIP6 CORDEX-CMIP6	CORDEX-CMIP5 CMIP5	0,100	
Rao, Prashanth	https://esgf-dn1.nsc.liu.se	Hard Disk	Continue to host existing data CMIP7 publication (and replication)	CMIP6	CMIP5 CORDEX-CMIP5	0,100	
Ratchanan Srisawadwong	https://esgf-dn1.ru.ac.th/ , https://esgf-dn1.ru.ac.th/thredds	Hard Disk	Continue to host existing data Other	Other CORDEX-CMIP6 CMIP6	CORDEX-CMIP5		

Table 5: Excerpt of the survey conducted by the CMIP IPO, including only the responses declaring participation or plans in the CORDEX data archival. Columns are: Primary contact name | Node identity | Current plans for storage and retrieval of historical ESGF data | Plans for 2025 and beyond | Active projects associated with the node | Archival projects associated with the node | Storage dedicated to CORDEX-CMIP5 (PB) | Storage dedicated to CORDEX-CMIP6 (PB).

Finally, in CORDEX-CMIP7 we could consider enhancing part of the data distribution from ESGF to cloud-based object storage, for example through services offered by the

European Open Science Cloud³⁹ (EOSC) or commercial providers such as AWS through open data sponsorships as was done for a small subset of EURO-CORDEX datasets⁴⁰ and NA-CORDEX⁴¹. Such a move would improve global accessibility, allow better co-location with cloud compute resources, and reduce the operational burden of maintaining a distributed network of ESGF mirrors. However, to take full advantage of the performance and scalability of cloud storage, data would likely need to be converted from traditional file-based NetCDF into the Zarr format. Zarr is designed for cloud object storage and enables efficient, parallel access to data over HTTP(S) or S3, which would support more flexible and scalable workflows for users. At the same time, adopting Zarr could help simplify some long-standing issues tied to the ESGF infrastructure, particularly the DRS directory structure, which is tightly coupled to traditional file-system-based storage. Because Zarr stores metadata within the dataset itself, it reduces the need for complex directory hierarchies and could make the overall system easier to maintain and extend. One caveat is that RCMs do not write directly to cloud storage, so at least initially data will still need to be stored on a traditional filesystem. For large datasets, Zarr data stores can consist of a huge number of files, which can be problematic with the number of filesystem inodes they take up. In practice, the workflow will likely need to still write the data to netCDF, CMORize, and then convert it to Zarr.

5.11 Errata

Errata refers to a record of errors found in the data and/or metadata after publication, along with their current status indicating whether a corrected version exists and potential problems in using the data as they are. In principle, once data are published, they should not be unpublished, as they could have been used for analyses that could not otherwise be replicated. Up to now, CORDEX has no centralized errata reporting system and different regional communities have set up their own solutions.

In CORDEX-CMIP5, in Europe, there is a [Google spreadsheet](#) listing the errors (the latest dates from 2021) and, more generally, [this website](#) which lists some other resources and instructs users to report problems via e-mail. For NAM, there are caveats⁴² (not exactly errata) and known issues⁴³. On top of this, there were a few CORDEX problems reported in the ES-Doc errata service (now under <https://errata.ipsl.fr>, selecting project “CORDEX”), that were collected there by the [C3S CDS](#). The ES-Doc developments are planned to continue under the framework of an ESGF Errata Service.

³⁹ <https://eosc.eu>

⁴⁰ <https://registry.opendata.aws/euro-cordex>

⁴¹ <https://registry.opendata.aws/ncar-na-cordex>

⁴² <https://na-cordex.org/caveats.html>

⁴³ <https://na-cordex.org/known-issues.html>

Some problems considering compliance with CF conventions were reported in [a github issue](#). These issues mainly came up when EURO-CORDEX datasets were intercompared and aggregated across different RCM models.

In CORDEX-CMIP6, there is no common approach, either. Although, in this case, there are no data officially published, so we are still in time to create a centralized errata system. In Australasia, there is this [website](#) collecting the errors in a table. In Europe, an errata system is still pending. The use of GitHub issues is still in discussion; this approach is being followed in [FPS-URB-RCC](#), where data problems can be discussed and errata reports can be generated (here [a mock-up example](#)). Also in [FPS-CONV](#).

In CORDEX-CMIP7, we should have a centralized errata system where users can find all potential problems in a single place. Plain text solutions facilitate long-term availability (unlike e.g. ES-Doc) and machine-readability facilitates the display of the information in various ways (e.g. selecting the errors for a particular regional domain, creating reports, etc.). It is especially important not to rely on dedicated infrastructures, developed for this task in specific projects and likely to be discontinued after the project ends. An errata system is something sufficiently simple to be maintained with very basic tools. The new ESGF Errata System to be created as a central hub to report and look up for data errors seems a promising way forward.

Errata, documentation (Section [5.7](#)) and guidelines (Section [5.9](#)) should be accessible from the ESGF, where data lives, so users can easily find how to interpret the data they are downloading and the errors they may contain. Another problem is that once data are downloaded, users rarely return to ESGF to find this information. Or, if a user finds the data in the filesystem, there is no way to know from where it was downloaded. Therefore, we might also consider adding in the archiving specifications (Section [5.6](#)) global metadata to all files, pointing to the errata, documentation and guidelines on how to use the entire ensemble (not just the individual file).

5.12 Monitoring the science

All of the above steps refer to CORDEX coordinated output data production, but this is just a means to perform coordinated downscaling science. Science monitoring refers to tracking the science enabled by CORDEX. This usually takes the shape of scientific publications, but also scientific projects and other science outputs (more informal analyses, applications in different platforms, etc.).

Since its inception, there is a central collection of scientific publications under [cordex.org](#). Several CORDEX initiatives (regional communities, FPS, ...) have duplicated this effort trying to collect publications in various ways (Table 6), in order to have a list of the publications relevant for their domain. Typically, publications are collected in websites or

documents, not really appropriate for further analysis or even collection. These are typically also easily outdated (Table 6), even though these need to be collected for the annual domain reports .

Initiative	Publication list	Updated
CORDEX	https://cordex.org/publications/peer-reviewed-publications	2024
AFR	https://www.csag.uct.ac.za/cordex-africa/cordex-africa-publications	2020
AUS	http://cordex-australasia.wikidot.com/publications	2011
EUR	https://euro-cordex.net/060380/index.php.en	2018
MED	https://www.medcordex.eu/publications.php	2025
MENA	https://mena-cordex.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/publications	2023
NAM	https://na-cordex.org/bibliography.html	2023
SEA	https://www.ukm.my/seaclid-cordex/Publications/Publications_2021.html	2021
FPS-CPTP	http://rcg.gvc.gu.se/cordex_fps_cptp/Publications.html	2024
FPS-CONV	https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/cordex-fps-conv/publications.html	2025

Table 6: Links to CORDEX publication lists for different initiatives. The last column shows the date of the latest publication reported.

Another option would be to use a proper bibliographic tool, such as the open source Zotero.org, which can expose the publications under different collections (e.g. per domain) and has an API to retrieve the data programmatically. A central collection of publications in such a tool would allow to track the CORDEX science by reporting the publications only once. The curation of the publications could be centralized in the regional POCs, who could gather into a common tool the info they are already collecting. And the other way around, help could be offered to the POCs to sync the information back into their regional websites in their preferred way. A similar attempt is in place in CMIP6⁴⁴. We created an example with this proposal⁴⁵, which is already feeding automatically the publication lists of the FPS-CONV and Med-CORDEX⁴⁶. It would be up to the regional communities to decide what is considered a CORDEX publication for their domain. Different categories could be created to monitor separately e.g. informal analyses, model

⁴⁴ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/publication-library>

⁴⁵ <https://www.zotero.org/groups/5816477/wcrp-cordex/library>

⁴⁶ <https://med-cordex.github.io/publications/publications.html>

documentation papers, community publications, publications using data from the corresponding CORDEX domain, etc.

Monitoring projects actually funding the CORDEX activity would also be key to track the science development. Central CORDEX funding via WCRP is very scarce; however, there is an unknown amount of funds raised worldwide and justified as contributing to CORDEX. Information on actually funded activities would help managing the initiative, planning for the future and making a better use of the few central resources at hand. CORDEX is truly about the coordination of research groups of very different size and resources, many of them running via small projects or simply in-kind. A potential return for the projects is to be shown as contributing to CORDEX, or even providing support letters in advance, if this helps funding agencies to decide. A tentative [form to collect relevant information](#) from projects has been set up as part of this TF.

6. Links to other task forces

The activity of this TF is strongly linked to the other ongoing TFs on Convection-permitting modelling (TF-CPM), on Regional ocean modelling and climate projections (TF-Ocean), on Machine learning (TF-ML), and on CORDEX-CORE (TF-CORE). In Section 5.2, we already remarked on several aspects of the experiment design step in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7 that are currently being discussed in those TFs. Here, we highlight some of the technical tasks in the realm of those TFs that could be carried out by the [WG proposed](#) as a result of this TF. These emerged during two cross-TF meetings held on 7th and 23rd July 2025.

From an organizational point of view, a second, cross-thematic WG could be useful to realize the experiment design step above (Section 5.2), integrating the expertise from different TFs, FPSs and beyond. Unlike the WGCI, this cross-thematic WG would benefit from experienced CORDEX researchers to develop a sound experimental design coordinating all emerging fields in the TFs and relevant FPSs. In any case, it is left for the TFs to decide how they would like to progress with their work after finalization and for the SAT to decide the new instruments to be implemented to accommodate the requests.

6.1 CORDEX-CORE

The CORDEX Coordinated Output for Regional Evaluations (CORDEX-CORE) initiative was launched to produce a homogeneous set of high-resolution climate projections using a standardized simulation protocol across domains ([Giorgi et al., 2022](#)). This involves downscaling a common set of GCMs with a common set of RCMs across most CORDEX continental domains, ensuring for each domain an ensemble of reasonable size as well as

the consistency and comparability of data across domains, for improved regional climate assessments and applications.

The TF-CORE was set up to alleviate the noticeable imbalance in CORDEX-CMIP6 in the literature and data availability across different CORDEX regions (see e.g. Figure 3). The TF aims to establish a protocol to ensure a homogeneous downscaled ensemble aligned with each CMIP cycle, fostering collaboration across CORDEX communities to address common research questions, such as climate mean and variability, extremes, and hazards, as well as scientific topics spanning multiple regions (e.g., monsoons, tropical and extratropical cyclones, teleconnection patterns). It also aims to build connections with initiatives like CMIP and HiResMIP, as well as the global impact modeling community (ISIMIP).

The TF in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7 will benefit from the development of TF-CORE in several aspects, starting with the experiment design, which, for CORDEX-CMIP7, should integrate the idea of CORE as starting point for the regional CORDEX Domain activity, instead of designing the CORE *a posteriori*, to fill homogeneity gaps. Thus, we envision CORDEX-CORE-CMIP7 as the initial CORDEX-CMIP7 DD protocol. CORDEX-CORE-CMIP7 would be a cross-domain experiment, to be considered by all regional communities along with their own experimental setup. Other cross-domain activities/experiments might make sense related to e.g. ML emulators (see [TF-ML](#) below).

This integration of the CORE experiment in the basic CORDEX experiment design entails an early development of the GCM selection (Section 5.3) and Data request (Section 5.5) steps. The efforts towards GCM selection in TF-CORE and TF-CMIP7 should facilitate an early global recommendation of driving GCMs in CORDEX-CMIP7, to be extended by the regional communities according to their own experiment setup. Also, the minimal Core set of variables prepared by TF-CORE can be used as a starting point for the CORDEX-CMIP7 Data request (Section 5.5), or even map the Core variables in the data request with the CORDEX-CORE data request.

And the other way around, TF-CMIP7 can provide support already for the CORDEX-CORE-CMIP6 experiment in all pending steps towards publication, that is: monitoring the simulations with [dedicated cross-domain experiments](#), supporting the [data request](#), generating the corresponding CMOR tables, and all remaining steps for CORDEX-CMIP6 in general (model documentation, quality control, guidelines, publication, errata and science monitoring).

6.2 Convection-permitting modelling

The Task Force on Convection Permitting Modelling (TF-CPM) focuses on advancing high-resolution regional climate simulations to better capture mesoscale processes and

improve the accuracy of climate projections, particularly for high-impact weather events. While current CORDEX ensembles provide valuable regional climate information, their standard resolution remains insufficient for resolving fine-scale features. Convection Permitting Regional Climate Models (CPRCMs) operating at kilometer-scale (1–4 km) grid spacing offer enhanced capability to simulate critical processes like orographic interactions and convective systems. However, challenges such as computational constraints, variable model fidelity, or limited high-resolution observations persist. This task force aims to address these gaps, evaluate the added value of CPRCMs compared to coarser models, and refine their application to improve local-scale climate projections.

TF-CPM is not developing specific archiving specifications, so these will need to be handled by the WGCI, taking into account the TF-CPM outcomes. One likely outcome are strong recommendations that modelling groups follow the CORDEX-defined archiving specifications as closely as possible and ensure that model output is FAIR and not stored on e.g., servers inaccessible to the public. The latter is accomplished by the publication of CPRCM output on ESGF. This can be facilitated by developing archiving specifications that take into account the particularities of CPRCMs. For instance, a mechanism needs to be established to propose domain definitions and to register them in the CORDEX CV to be used for ESGF publication. A new `activity_id` might be necessary (beyond DD) to account for the specificities of CPM, such as the potential use of intermediate domains. Some examples of how to [handle these intermediate nests](#) have been developed in the framework of the FPS-CONV.

TF-CPM will not be defining specific domains but will make some recommendations that the community should try to follow to avoid many overlapping CP domains. There might need to be a term-limited working group that serves as a node to coordinate between CPRCM experiments and the broader community.

The computational demand of CPM will likely impact the time span and uncertainty sampling of the simulations. This opens the floor for emerging techniques, such as emulators, which link with the TF-ML. CPM scales are also reached in the context of several small islands-focused FPSs, which started recently (FPS-IC-Pac, FPS-I-Mac and FPS-TC-Car). Clear communication channels need to be established between these FPSs and the TF-CPM, to ensure compatible protocols among them. In this context, the coupling to the ocean will be key, linking also to the TF-Ocean. Potential links are also expected with TF-CORE, e.g. in the selection of driving GCMs or, more specifically, to provide enough driving fields to use CORDEX-CORE data sets as intermediate nests for CPM. The latter poses great strain to the CORDEX-CORE data request, so a careful selection of the simulations to be used as intermediate nests will likely be needed.

6.3 Ocean

The CORDEX TF on regional ocean climate projections ([TF-Ocean](#)) is a joint CORDEX-CLIVAR OMDP (Ocean Model Development Panel) initiative that is developing an experiment protocol to provide more granular regional-to-local ocean climate information for the historical and future climate change scenarios. This is to be initially achieved using dynamical Ocean Regional Climate Models (ORCMs) and is to be informed by the experience of the regional ocean modelling community.

The experiment protocols for downscaling the CMIP7 generation of GCMs is also currently being developed for the CORDEX Ocean TF. This includes developing experimental, validation and archiving protocols and establishing simulation domains and resolution, which are broadly consistent with those used for CORDEX atmosphere downscaling. Simulation domains are informed by regions used in AR6 to ensure relevance for the scientific community, with a position paper currently in development. Experiment design is to support Ocean climate services, as well as advance the science of regional ocean projections. This includes sea level rise in coastal zones, marine ecosystems, ocean mixing and polar regions.

TF-Ocean is, thus, dealing with the ocean modelling science, but also with many of the technical protocols and documentation steps proposed in TF-CMIP7. Rather than separate protocols, the recommendation would be to integrate naturally the ocean component as part of the protocols for dynamical downscaling. TF-CMIP7 in cooperation with the Med-CORDEX community is already testing for CORDEX-CMIP6 several approaches to integrate the ocean component in the [data request](#), [archiving specifications](#) and [model documentation](#). These will hopefully be good starting points for CORDEX-CMIP7. A major challenge is the publication of oceanic data, as they are typically defined on different grids and might cover different areas as compared to the atmospheric component. Input from TF-Ocean will also be key for the driving GCM selection, to take into account oceanic metrics relevant to this component.

TF-Ocean is planning two different protocols, one for coupled AORCMs and another for uncoupled ORCMs. The latter have never been considered in CORDEX, so this is a question remaining for the experimental design of CORDEX-CMIP7, whether these ocean-only regional simulations can be included under the CORDEX umbrella. Related to this, TF-Ocean is planning new “continental” regions over large oceanic areas (e.g. in the Pacific, where many islands would be covered).

Finally, TF-Ocean is collecting existing regional ocean simulations, for which there was no CORDEX protocol. In order for these data to feed AR7, they should be published before the cut-off for data publication (possibly by mid 2027). We need to assess whether these could fit under the CORDEX-CMIP6 ESGF project or a new project needs to be set up. In

any case, some homogenization work would be necessary to e.g. reconcile the simulations domains used by these independent simulations.

6.4 Machine Learning

TF-ML aims to develop a strategic plan to coordinate machine learning-based downscaling activities. This will require collaboration and coordination with relevant external initiatives, which will be identified through a landscaping activity to assess the current status of the field. Within CORDEX, this TF has strong links with ongoing regional (e.g. [Baño-Medina et al., 2022](#)), FPS (FPS-SSA-ML, FPS-IC-Pac, FPS-I-Mac, ...) and TF activities; particularly the TF-CPM, to align km-scale downscaling activities, and TF-CORE, to extend the size of the ensemble. TF-ML was launched to promote best practices, and facilitate knowledge exchange to address key challenges in the field.

A close collaboration will also be needed with TF-CMIP7 to integrate the ML activities in the CORDEX-CMIP7 experiment design and the development of dedicated archiving specifications to enable ML output data publication. ML can be used as a methodology for downscaling in the framework of standard ESD approaches (Perfect Prog, Bias Adjustment), as well as in the framework of RCM emulators ([Doury et al., 2023](#)), especially useful at CPM scale to replace costly CPRCM simulations. All these activities are being analysed and tested in CORDEX-CMIP6 and full implementation (following experimental and archiving protocol) is envisaged for CORDEX-CMIP7 and require the development of corresponding technical protocols to support them. Good starting points are the current draft of the [CORDEX experiment design and archiving specifications for statistical downscaling of CMIP6](#) and the [Description of the DRS for archiving results of statistical and emulation-based downscaling](#) (Deliverable 3.4 in the EU-funded project IMPETUS4CHANGE), which extends the ESD archiving specifications to RCM emulators. Essentially, all steps in TF-CMIP7 will need to take into account the particularities of ML/ESD, which will be made explicit as a result of the TF-ML.

One requirement from the TF-ML for CORDEX-CMIP7 is the selection of scenarios, particularly the inclusion of the highest plausible one (e.g., as SSP3-7.0 in CMIP6), to ensure robust training of emulators.

Benchmarking (one of the activities of the TF-ML) involves the preparation of test GCM-RCM datasets to train and test ML-based downscaling methods. The selection of relevant GCM-RCM examples and representative domains (continental and CP-subdomains) could be also a topic for coordination with TF-CORE and TF-CPM, with the potential to expand the initial benchmark focusing on continental domains to CP simulation scales.

7. Timeline

The timeline for the preparatory steps discussed in this document are very tight. The first outputs from CMIP7 AFT are expected by early 2026. A CMIP Community Workshop will take place in March 2026 (<https://wcrp-cmip.org/event/cmip26>), marking a turning point in CMIP7–AFT data availability. Figure 4 shows a tentative timeline for the steps proposed to meet the IPCC AR7 deadlines. A few key dates act as milestones when some of the steps should start or end. Namely, we marked the CORDEX SAT Extended Meeting to be held in Hamburg (Germany) on November 10–14th, 2025. A number of key decisions should be taken at this meeting, which should mark the kick-off of the CORDEX-CMIP7 long-term strategy. Preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7–AFT should start ahead of this meeting and be used to provide input for decisions. Note that the timeline shown is for the steps in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7–AFT, while the longer-term CORDEX-CMIP7 strategy planning should be shifted by about 6 months with respect to this figure. In this way, the development of each CORDEX-CMIP7–AFT step transitions to the development of the extension for the longer-term strategy. Note also that, for most of these steps, TF-CMIP7 has developed strategy proposals that have been applied to CORDEX-CMIP6.

Step termination (abrupt or open-ended) is determined by the cut-off dates for article and data publication to be established by the IPCC WGI. The diagram in Figure 4 shows current estimates.

To meet the deadlines, step development phases need to span 6 months in most cases, although some steps benefiting from prior CORDEX-CMIP6 work could be ready faster (they span 3 months in the scheme). Note that this is completely unprecedented in CORDEX, since many of these steps have traditionally taken several years to develop. We will need strong and quick community involvement and dedicated Task Teams to be appointed for each step in order to be able to develop all these steps in parallel in such record-breaking time. All this activity should be supervised by a very active Working Group on CORDEX Infrastructure (WGCI, see Appendix 3).

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the timeline for steps in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT to meet the deadlines of IPCC AR7. The bars representing the TF-proposed steps span the development and maintenance phases of each step, while the CORDEX stages show preparation, simulation, and science phases (see legend). Activities with flat ends are expected to finish at the corresponding date, while arrow-headed ones may extend beyond that point and should preferably be ready by then. The red line marks the time of writing: left of this line, dates are accurate; right of the line, dates are estimates.

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Appendix 1: Survey on potential commitments for CORDEX-CMIP7 in time for AR7

This [survey](#) was launched on April 15th, 2025, as part of the work in the CORDEX Task Force (TF) in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7. The questions collect prior knowledge of existing national or institutional commitments to downscale the CMIP7 Fast Track in time for AR7 or other assessments/adaptation plans in the short term. It also covers some details on model development plans and longer term commitment for CORDEX-CMIP7, beyond the IPCC AR7 deadlines.

All data collected are treated confidentially, so here we share only aggregated statistics. In any case, the answers from the modelling groups are non-binding and for exploratory purposes only. Actual, detailed CORDEX-CMIP7 plans will be collected in the future (see Section 5.4).

The survey collects some initial information for future reference (full name, contact email, institution) and then some multiple-choice and free text questions collect detailed information which is summarized next for the 24 responses received as of Jul 30th, 2025. No discussion of the results is included in this Appendix, but key figures are replicated and discussed in the main document where appropriate.

Questions

Downscaling model type

Select just one. If multiple models are used in your institution/group, please, fill out one survey per model.

- ESD (Empirical-statistical downscaling)
- RCM-emulator
- ARCM (prescribed-SST RCM)
- AORCM (ocean-coupled RCM)
- AGCM (prescribed-SST GCM, including variable-resolution models)
- AOGCM (ocean-coupled GCM, including variable-resolution models)
- Other...

- ARCM (prescribed-SST RCM)
- AOGCM (ocean-coupled GCM, including variable-resolution models)
- AORCM (ocean-coupled RCM)
- Other ("All")
- RCM-emulator
- ESD (Empirical-statistical downscaling)

What were the main challenges you faced during the downscaling of CMIP6 data?

Please select up to three of the most significant barriers.

- We did not participate in CORDEX-CMIP6
- Insufficient computing resources
- Limited data storage capacity
- CMORization process
- Lack of funding
- Insufficient personnel
- Ongoing model development
- Other...

Do you have a newer version of your downscaling model (as compared to CORDEX-CMIP6) ready to be used?

- Yes
 No

If yes, please, comment briefly how has your model evolved

Free text.

Answers (8):

- Inclusion of regional carbon cycle and double moment cloud microphysics.
- New urban parameterization
- new dynamical core

- Resolution change through New TCO Grid
- Now able to activate additional components, such as the urban model
- We have changed the RCM from RegCM4 to the coupled model, COAWST.
- Ocean coupling, improvements in model setup and parameterizations
- Various improvements consistent with the Hadley Centre GCM configuration.

Are you planning to downscale CMIP7 Fast Track simulations in time for AR7 (downscaled data available by mid-2027) over any of the CORDEX domains?

- Yes
- Yes, but only if there's a coordinated effort in the domain
- Depends on funding, which is likely to be available
- Depends on funding, which is not likely to be available
- No
- Other ...

- Yes
- Yes, but only if there's a coordinated effort in the domain
- Depends on funding, which is likely to...
- Depends on funding, which is not likel...
- No
- Probably no if the AR7 expected dead...
- That is the intention in my group, we a...
- Probably no if the AR7 expected dead...
- Probably no if the AR7 expected dead...

Are you planning to downscale CMIP7 simulations at some point (after AR7) over any of the CORDEX domains?

- Yes
- Yes, but only if there's a coordinated effort in the domain
- Depends on funding, which is likely to be available
- Depends on funding, which is not likely to be available
- No
- Other ...

- Yes
- Yes, but only if there's a coordinated effort in the domain
- Depends on funding, which is likely to be available
- Depends on funding, which is not likel...
- No
- Will downscaled for regions appropriat...
- The goal is the fast track so that the in...
- Plan to downscale all available CMIP7...

Which domain(s) would you be planning to downscale?

Check all that apply.

Do you have an in-house or preferred CMIP7 GCM to provide input for your simulations?

If yes, which one(s)?

Do you have a commitment to downscale a particular scenario or scenario family?

If yes, which would be your preferred/required family?

[Van Vuuren et al. \(2025\)](#) propose a classification (see Table 1) based on emissions as: High (H), Medium (M), Medium-Low (ML), Low (L), Very Low with Limited Overshoot (VLLO), Very Low after High Overshoot (VLHO). Overshoot scenarios would be complementary to CMIP6 SSPs as they have not been thoroughly explored, while the others could be compared with existing SSP concentration-driven scenarios. You can also state your overall preference/needs rather than specific scenario families.

Free text.

- We have no specific commitment yet but to downscale at least an overshoot scenario (VLLO or VLHO), not yet chosen. Usually we also like to downscale at least one high emission scenario to help training emulators. Besides, our national climate service tends to push for the downscaling of “realistic” scenarios and/or to cover a given list of GWL or RWL (not yet chosen for CMIP7 scenario).
- H, M & L
- Not yet. But might come.
- We downscale all CMIP runs and all emission scenarios since our ESD is designed to run extremely efficiently. However we downscale only seasonal surface air temperature and precipitation statistics.
- Not yet decided.
- H, M and if capacity allows ML

Thank you for your input. Please, use the space below for any final clarification or comment regarding CORDEX-CMIP7

Free text.

- Our main focus in the coming 2 years is on finishing the CORDEX-CMIP6 exercise, publish the runs on the ESGF and write associated publications, in particular to feed AR7 with well-established and well-validated multi-model ensembles for our domains of interest.

Then we would like to have time to develop the new versions of the regional climate models, in particular to develop the model complexity before starting a new production cycle.

Finally, it is not clear for us at this stage what will be the good balance between RCM, RESM, CPRCM and Emulators for CORDEX-CMIP7. This leads to uncertainties in our answers.

We also would like to underline that currently the separation between the CMIP7 FT and the CMIP7 community MIP is unclear in particular in terms of GCM version.

- Since my interest is dynamic downscaling and isotope enabled GCMs, we have also reach out to a colleague that has been working with the statistical downscaling to integrate efforts of both groups.
- ESD will be applied to all available GCM runs since it can be run on a laptop with monthly GCM output. Our approach is different to traditional ESD which makes it suitable for downscaling large multi-model ensembles and all emission scenarios.

Appendix 2: Survey on climate forcing data used in CORDEX-CMIP6

A quick e-mail survey was run on the different climate forcing data used by the different models:

Could you please provide feedback on the following questions regarding the RCM you are currently using in CORDEX-CMIP6:

1. *Are you considering a fixed solar constant (which value?) or using an evolving total solar irradiance consistent with your driving GCM?*
2. *What GHG species does your model consider?*
3. *What granularity of GHG concentrations are you using (e.g. annual global means, monthly latitudinal distribution, ...)? Is your model capable of ingesting a different granularity for these data?*
4. *Is your model capable of dealing with GHG and/or aerosols emissions instead of concentrations/AODs?*
5. *For any of the questions above, do you expect your model development in the next 5 years or so to change any of the answers above?*

Here is a summary of the answers so far:

Model (contact)	Solar constant	GHG species	GHG granularity	Emissions-ready?	Expected changes
HCLIM43-ALADIN (G. Nikulin)	Evolving according to input4MIPS	CO2 CH4 N2O CFC11 CFC12 and climatology for O3	Annual global means only	No	Most likely no
CRCM5 and CRCM6-GEM5 (D. Paquin)	1361 W/m2	CO2 N2O CH4 CFC11-eq CFC12	Annual global means only	No	Not really
CCAM (M. Thatcher)	Evolving according to input4MIPS	CO2 CH4 N2O CFC11 CFC12 CFC113 HCFC22	Monthly global means only	AOD yes, GHG no	We can utilise emissions for the carbon cycle, but we would require concentrations for the GHG (e.g., CH4, N2O, CFCs) as well as ozone. CCAM has a prognostic terrestrial carbon cycle model (CASA-CNP), which would create its own natural terrestrial carbon emissions as well as modifying vegetation properties (e.g., leaf area index for browning of vegetation).

BARPA (Chun Hus Su)	1361 W/m2	CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC11, CFC12, SO4, CFC113, HCFC22, HFC125, HFC134a and CFC114	Annual global means only	Emissions could be handled via UKCA and the GLOMAP aerosol scheme – however this would be expensive and isn't on our radar.	Aerosol forcing is prescribed as monthly and 3D-varying. I don't think we're planning model development in this area at this time. However, if there was a big push for a particular development and not too resource intensive, we could revise this.
RegCM5 (G. Giuliani)	Evolving according to input4MIPS SOLARIS-HE PPA-3-2_gn_ 185001-2299 12	CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC11, CFC12	For CMIP6, using input4MIPS data, i.e. monthly, latitude dependency. For CMIP5, yearly annual global mean.	Possibly, activating transport. CHEM model (CBMZ, 4/12 dust, SSLT, OC/BC, SULF modules possible. Aerosol emission from the surface using CLM4.5). Computati onal cost involved. For aerosol CMIP6, using now Simple Plume model from CMIP6 Input4MIP S.	Chemistry model under development by Fabien Solmon, OSU-CNRS, may switch out from CBMZ
RACMO23E (E. van Meijgaard)	Evolving according to input4MIPS	CO2 N2O CH4, CFC11-eq CFC12	Annual global means only	No	At the moment, I do not foresee any effort in that direction.
CanRCM5 (J. Scinocca)	Evolving	CO2 CFC11-eq, CFC12 CH4 N2O	Annual global means, but the model is based on a global ESM and so can support 3D CO2 if lateral	Yes	Possibly

			boundary conditions are supplied.		
ICON-CLM (C. Steger)	Evolving according to input4MIPS v3.2	CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC_11, CFC_12	Annual global means only	No	Emissions will be implemented in ICON for CMIP7 in the global configuration. Not sure, if this can be used in the limited-area mode (closed carbon cycle, ocean + biogeochemistry needed). Question 4: yes. Question 1-3 unknown. For the time being, implementations were transferred from ECHAM6 to ICON-ECHAM to ICON-NWP (which is the physics package used by ICON-CLM).
CNRM-ALADIN64 E1	Evolving, based on CMIP6 forcings, Matthes et al. 2017	CO2 N2O CH4 CFC-11-eq CFC-12	Annual global means only	interactive aerosol scheme (TACTIC, Nabat et al. 2020), which uses anthropogenic and biomass burning emissions. Not possible for GHG.	Interactive chemistry could be available in the coming years. Our model is not able to ingest a different GHG granularity for the moment (but monthly global means could be considered with adaptation work)
WRF (G. di Virgilio)	1368.2 W/m2	CO2 N2O CH4 CFC11 CFC12	Annual SH means	No (too heavy CHEM option)	I think handling of aerosols (4) is a likely candidate for change in future.
REMO2020 (L. Buntmeyer)	Fixed	CO2 N2O CH4 CFC11 CFC12	Annual global means	No	Including TEB for urban parameterization

CFC11-eq: The effects of the remaining GHG of the original data set (39 species) are grouped into a single CFC11-eq species, following the option 2 of Meinshausen et al. (2017).

Appendix 3: Proposal for an upcoming Working Group on CORDEX Infrastructure

In this Appendix⁴⁷, we propose a way forward for the work started in this Task Force. The idea would be to create a Working Group on CORDEX Infrastructure (WGCI). Working Groups, in this sense, would be a new instrument with a long term mission in support of CORDEX. In this case, the mission of WGCI would be to supervise, develop and maintain all the scientific infrastructure that supports CORDEX. This includes central software, metadata, controlled vocabularies, technical documentation, etc., and is related to essentially all steps (Section 5) described in this document.

Task Teams (TTs) could be created by the WG for specific tasks with a precise outcome and deadline. These could be used for many specific steps in this document. TTs would be composed of WG members and additional external people required for the task (e.g. representatives with background in ESGF, CF, CMIP, ...).

This is a very technical and time-demanding activity. Thus, enthusiastic early-career scientists (ECS) are good candidates for the WG and associated TTs. Regardless of their expertise, members should be technically skilled to operate with the tools to be used to implement the steps.

- Experts for different models/approaches
- POCs from different domains
- Representatives from TF themes
- Representatives from the CORDEX-SAT
- Expertise beyond CORDEX (CMIP, Climate forcings, CORDEX output users)

Even if the TF has a mandate to prepare for CORDEX-CMIP7, the WGCI should also handle some remaining steps in CORDEX-CMIP6, which can then be aligned to fit as much as possible the upcoming CORDEX-CMIP7, as they will likely coexist in time.

WGCI would presumably work openly via GitHub and resort often to consultants for specific topics who can dedicate smaller amounts of time, but can focus on specific issues.

⁴⁷ We keep in this Appendix the original TF proposal for a Working Group. However, due to the urgency of the tasks, the CORDEX SAT proposed the creation of a Task Team on Protocols and Infrastructure (TTPI) to move forward all these aspects of CORDEX-CMIP7. A [call](#) was launched in October 2025 and this Task Team was finally approved during the Open SAT meeting in Hamburg (17–21 Nov 2025), starting its term immediately (end of 2025).

This document has been written as a guideline for such WGCI, with plenty of details for each step, including past actions and strategies and many links to further information. It has been delivered way ahead of the TF appointed deadline to make room for the WG call while the TF is still active, so we transition smoothly to the new team. We offer ourselves for a candidate pre-selection and to make a draft proposal of the WG composition to the SAT.

One step in preparation for CORDEX-CMIP7 that could hardly be handled by the WGCI just proposed above is the experiment design (Section 5.2). This requires very experienced CORDEX representatives with expertise in different fields. Time-availability would also be a constraint, but this alternative WG could go on as an executive science body between the SAT and the community, to actually carry out the developments, assisted by the more technical WGCI. If POCs are encouraged to be part of this WG, it would also serve the purpose of enhancing cross-domain interaction. PoCs are also much welcome in the WGCI, so the regional communities would ideally have representatives in the science advisory, executive and technical bodies. Alternatively, the experiment design could be assigned to a TT dedicated to this task with a given deadline and requiring members with deeper CORDEX expertise in different fields.

All these WGs and TTs should be active in a very short time in order to meet the tight deadlines of CORDEX-CMIP7-AFT (see Section 7).